

Coverage of Sustainable Development Goals (I-IV) By The Daily Trust and The Guardian Newspapers

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Abstract

Nations of the world met in September 2015 at the United Nations Headquarters, New York and adopted the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) the successor framework to the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) which came to an end in 2015. The leaders agreed to set the world on a path towards Sustainable Development through the adoption of the 2030 agenda. This agenda includes 17 Sustainable Development Goals which form a cohesive and integrated package of global aspiration of the world that set out three quantitative dimensions of 'Sustainable Development' of economic growth, environmental sustainability and social inclusion. Nigeria is bedevilled with multiple development challenges ranging from poverty, hunger, diseases, lack of qualitative education among others. However, due to the powerful influence of media in reinforcing social change, it came to be associated with development; media were considered as valuable instrument in contributing towards eradicating of those societal challenges. Consequently, the study examines the extent to which the Nigerian press cover the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) I-IV using quantitative content analysis as the research methodology. A Census technique was applied in content analysing two Nigerian newspapers (*Daily Trust* and *The Guardian*) for twelve months 2016 was the study time frame. Also, 520 copies of the two newspapers were analysed and interpreted using a descriptive method of data analysis. Moreover, Agenda Settings and Media Framing formed the study theoretical framework. The study findings revealed that the coverage of SDGs I-IV was significantly low as compared to other study content categories. On the other hand, the level of prominence accorded to SDGs I-IV was also significantly low in comparison to other SDGs and Non-SDGs. In addition, the direction of SDGs I-IV coverage was highly recorded as positive or promotional to SDGs development agenda. Finally, the study recommended that further studies should be carried out using both the quantitative and qualitative approach to have a clear understanding in a more analytical mode. It is also important to sensitise media professionals about the need to improve the quantity and quality of SDGs coverage in Nigeria which should include articles and analysis reflecting everyday struggles of regions especially

IJARBAS

Accepted 20 February 2023
Published 28 February 2023
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7770878

the condition of those living in resource-poor settings. Doing so will help encouraging societies and decision-makers to prioritise the SDGs agenda in the decision making process.

Keywords: Sustainable Development Goals (I-IV), Daily Trust and The Guardian, SDGs I-IV, Coverage of Sustainable Development Goals,

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study.....	1
1.2 Problem Statement.....	5
1.3 Aim of the Study.....	7
1.4 Objectives of the Study.....	7
1.5 Research Questions.....	8
1.6 Significance of the Study.....	9
1.7 Scope and Limitations of the Study.....	9
1.8 Operational Definition of Terms.....	10

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Development Communication: An Overview.....	11
2.2 Development, Media and SDGs.....	13
2.3 Role of Media in Development Communication.....	17
2.4 Review of Related Literature	20
2.5 Theoretical Framework	33
2.5.1 Agenda Setting Theory.....	34
2.5.1.1. Types of Agenda Setting Theory.....	34
2.5.1.2 Limitations to Agenda Setting Theory.....	35
2.5.1.1 Relevance of the Theory to the Study.....	36
2.5.2 Media Framing Theory.....	37
2.5.2.1 Types of Frames.....	38
2.5.2.2 Limitations to Framing theory.....	39
2.5.2.3 Relevance of the Theory to the Study.....	39

CHAPTER THREE RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design	40
3.2 Universe of the Study.....	41

3.3 Sample Size.....	43
3.4 Sampling Technique.....	43
3.5 Units of Analysis.....	45
3.6 Content Categories.....	46
3.7 Definition of Content Categories.....	47
3.8 Coding and Measurement of Content Categories	56
3.9 Inter-Coder Reliability.....	57
3.10 Methods of Data Presentation and Analysis.....	59
3.11 Newspapers Profile Under Study.....	59
3.11.1 The Guardian Newspaper.....	59
3.11.2 The Daily Trust.....	61

**CHAPTER FOUR
DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS**

4.1 Results from the Analysis of Daily Trust and the Guardian Newspapers.....	62
4.2 Frequency of occurrence of SDGs I-IV in comparison to other SDGs: Discussion of Findings.....	64
4.3 Story Positioning/ prominence of SDGs I-IV in comparison to other SDGs: Discussion of Findings.....	73
4.4 Direction of Coverage of SDGs I-IV by Daily Trust and The Guardian Newspapers: Discussion of Findings.....	76
4.5 Sources/ Major players of SDGs I-IV coverage of SDGs by Daily Trust and The Guardian Newspapers: Discussion of Findings.....	83
4.6 Journalistic genres used in the coverage of SDGs I-IV by Daily Trust and The Guardian Newspapers: Discussion of Findings.....	87
4.7 Summary of Major Findings.....	90

**CHAPTER FIVE
SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS**

5.1 Summary.....	91
5.2 Conclusion.....	93
5.3 The Study's Contribution to Knowledge	95
5.4 Recommendations for Further Studies	95
References.....	97 -104
Appendix i	
Coding Sheets for Data Collection.....	105
Appendix ii	
2016 Calendar.....	113

CHAPTER ONE: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

The idea of building a better world through globally organized development framework started with the idea of the Millennium Development Goals, (MDGs), despite the optimism that surrounded it, the United Nations recognized that not all the goals were met and it would take a longer time to get parts of the world to meet the goals. So another related but more expansive goals were developed and called the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in 2015. Countries around the world, including Nigeria subscribed to the SDGs, aimed at transforming the world- a call to action to end poverty and inequality, protect the planet and ensure that all people benefit from health, prosperity and justice. This is the basic message of the SDGs. One institution that can contribute to the realization of the SDGs is the media. In all cases of development, the media have been considered useful and could contribute to the facilitation of processes of development.

Communication scholars have provided various perspectives on what the media can do to facilitate or promote development. There is a debate on what role the media can play in development. The belief that the media can play a role led to the emergence of the discipline called development communication. However, all the scholars that were involved in the analysis and application of communication for development was assumed to believed that:

Development communication is the sharing of knowledge aimed at reaching a consensus for action that take into account the interest, needs, and capacities of all concerned. It is thus a social process. Communication media are important tools in achieving this process. (Servaes, 2002 p.3).

The basic consensus on the concept of development communication has been interpreted and applied into different perspectives throughout the past centuries both through the theory and the policy levels. For instance, the mode of development communication studies within the period of 1958-1986 was purely more in theoretical framework the studies also provide a major role of communication to the socio- economic development of less developed nations as enunciated by Joe Ellien Fair in her PhD thesis summarized in the journal gazette, 1989 cited in Servaes, (2002, P.2)

Communication has been a key element in the West's project of developing the Third world. In the one- and-a-half decades after Lerner's influential 1958 study of communication researchers assumed that the introduction of media and certain types of educational, political, and economic information into a social systems could transform individuals and societies from traditional to modern. Conceived as having fairly direct and powerful effects on Third World audiences, the media were seen as magic multipliers, able to accelerate and magnify the benefits of development.

However, around 1987-1996, the most frequent suggestion was "the need to conduct more policy research, including institutional analysis of development agency coordination. This was followed by the need to research and develop indigenous models of communication and development through participatory research" (Fair & Shah, 1997, p.19) cited in (Servaes, 2002, p.2). Meanwhile, The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) Framework as agreed by all the 189 member states of the United Nations (UN), is expected to commit other stakeholders including businesses and civil society organisations and above all, the media to the achievement of the 17 Goals, 169 targets and 230 indicators spanning the three integrated dimensions of economic growth, social inclusion and environmental protection. The success of one leads to the success of all. Included in this is the need for good governance and strong social networks which translate into a framework focused on people, the planet, prosperity, peace and partnership. (UN Report, 2015).

The Mass Media, on the other, hand are considered as having a major function in all societies of information dissemination through the process of gathering and managing of information and ideas. The media can create awareness, knowledge, change attitudes, and transform behaviours, foster engagement and supports in formulating sound national policies which are elements that transform societies towards growth and development (McQuail, 2005)

In the same vein, the issue of development has over the years become one of the issues the mass media are exposed to, theorist like Schramm (1964) have advocated the importance of the media in the development process of a nation. According to him, the media are expected to explain, inform, and educate society on crucial issues affecting society's well being and progress. On this note, Aggarwala (1979), an advocate of development communication assumed that the media have become pervasive instrumentalities of modern existence.

The media which comprised radio, television, newspapers, magazines and the internet have been described by Edmund Burke in the late Eighteenth century as the fourth Estate of the Realm or the fourth branch of government, apart from the Executive legislature and judiciary (McQuail, 2006). However, due to the powerful influence of media in reinforcing social change, it came to be associated with development. The attainment of sustainable development depends on the socio-economic and political environment, as the role of the media becomes pervasive. The media are meant to serve both elites and the people at the grassroots levels. They are expected to focus their time and resources on sensitive issues that matter most to the people.

Considering the importance of development news to the resolution of societal problems International Press Institute (IPS) published a book named *Reporters Guide to the*

Millennium Development Goals: Covering Development Commitment for 2015 and beyond narrating how crucial development news is to the citizenry. Alioson Bethel Makenzie – Executive Director International Press Institute stated that “ ...the guide intended to inspire and encourage reporters and their editors to dig deeper and give development stories higher priority on newspaper pages, airwaves, and Worldwide Web” (Guerrero & Griffen, 2013, p.5).

Nigeria, a member of the United Nations, has numerous daunting developmental challenges ranging from extreme poverty, hunger, illiteracy, lack of adequate health facilities, environmental instability, poor security condition among others. Because of these challenges, the country appeared committed to ownership, integration and realization of the SDGs goals. The first major step was the establishment of a special office on SDGs which is being hosted within the presidency. This special office, as expressed by President Muhammad Buhari’s report on the *Implementation of SDGs: A National Voluntary Review*, (2017, p.v)

The Nigerian government provides key policy, institutional as well as regulatory measures that have been put in place to create the necessary enabling environment for mainstreaming of the SDGs into national policies and plans, as well as programmes along with the necessary coherent coordination.

Implementation of developmental programmes like SDGs was described as the responsibility of all. Apart from governing bodies, journalists have a significant role among the many incorporated stakeholders towards the realization of the global, universal and developmental efforts of Sustainable Development Goals. The then United Nations (UN) Secretary-General, Kofi Annan, declared that... “The issue we are dealing with from the elimination of poverty to the fight against AIDS and the protection of the environment are issues that require all hands on deck (Griffen, 2013, p.11). He expatiates

more on the issue: “Indeed, it would be a grave error to think that only government have the power to further the MDGs. Such a conclusion is an invitation to skepticism if we reflect that, left to their own devices, government bodies at both national and international levels may decline to prioritize human and social development or lose interest in the MDGs altogether” (Griffen, 2013, p.11).

Considering the complexity and the breadth of the goals themselves, it is clear that government is just one factor in the success of the SDGs. Civil Society Groups have the task of compiling statistics and defending the rights of the vulnerable; private donors and philanthropists bring critical funds to the most needed part, scientists and universities lead research for identification of workable and innovative solutions. As for the journalists, they are the most important element. (Griffen, 2013, p. 12).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The press in Nigeria were not giving a considerable attention to their constitutional role of fostering national development, little attention was paid to the coverage of development news while, significant attention was mainly concentrated to sensational news that has little relevance to the majority of populace.

It is normal to see a large portrait of political leaders, top government functionaries or public office holders on a newspaper front page. A newspaper reader can also testify major stories of political parties’ controversies over office sharing appearing boldly in Nigerian newspapers’ headlines. An element of importance is only attached to the prominence of the people involved in the story in contrast to the significance the story has to the majority of the populace. The media is considered as the fourth estate of the realm has a tremendous role to foster national development. They are one important key element in the functioning towards implementation of developmental programmes (Yusha’u, 2014; Salawu, 2003; Jimoh, 2007;

Best, 2005). A developing Nigerian nation is bedeviled with multiple development problems. Despite its huge resources Nigeria, being the Africa leading economy with the highest economic growth rate of 7.4%, nonetheless, poverty remains significant at 33 percent of the population (World Bank, Nigeria Economic Report, July, 2014). Meanwhile, the country has a population of over 190 million people according to statistics provided by the National Bureau Statistics (NBC), October, 2016 this shows that the population living in poverty in the country rose to 68.7 million in 2004, to 112.5 million in 2010 (Kale, 2012 cited in Ibada, 2014), indicating an increase in the population living in poverty instead of reduction.

Hunger is also rampant among the people with the growing negative increase of people especially children living with mal-nutrition and undernourishment. Meanwhile, a joint report from United Nations (UN) and European Union (EU) released in April, 2019 shows that Nigeria appeared to be one of the countries that experienced the worst food crisis in the world in 2018. In connection to this challenge, the number of people unable to meet their daily food needs without humanitarian assistance has been rising for several years (Global Report on Food Crises, 2019 cited in Toromade, 2019). Meanwhile, data pooled from 15 Agencies in the International humanitarian and development community showed that Nigeria, Northern Nigeria to be specific was one of the eight countries that housed two-third of the 113 million people who faced acute hunger across the globe in 2018 amounting to 72 million people leaving in acute hunger.

More so, the report of the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) indicated that in 2013 300,000 women die annually during pregnancy and childbirth, three million babies do not survive the first months of life, while 2.5 million were born with the majority in Africa. Nigeria alone lost 2,300 under five years old and 145 women during childbirth in a day making it the second-largest contributor to the under-five and maternal mortality rate in the

world (Child Health Survey by UNICEF, 2015). In addition, the HIV/AIDS adult prevalence rate was 3.17% in 2014 while the number of people living with it was 3,391,600 which is about 2.7% (Nigeria Demographic Profile, 2016). These indicate the poor state of health delivery in the country. It is evident that many school children are still on the street hawking or being trafficked for domestic slavery.

The press/media were considered as a valuable instrument in contributing towards eradicating the above stated societal problems; the media can also be employed to subject the SDG's policies, and strategies chosen to meet them for informed public debate. Similarly, they are regarded as magic multipliers having the powerful ability to accelerate and magnify the benefits of development (Fair, 1989) cited in (Seavaes, 2008).

It is against this backdrop that this study intends to examine the extent to which the Nigerian press covers Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) specifically goals I-1V. Apart from the few research that was conducted on the concept of Sustainable development in the field of journalism. The researcher becomes interested to find out the development so far gained in the period under study that is 2016 on this global effort of impacting significant improvement in the life and well-being of Nigerian people.

1.3 Aim of the Study

The aim of the study is to examine newspaper coverage of development issues SDGs goals (I-IV) by the Nigerian newspapers (*Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers) for one year that is 2016, using editorials, news stories, news analysis and features/opinions as the units of analysis.

1.4 Objectives of the Study

It's part of the objectives of this study to:

1. To identify the issues of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) covered by Daily Trust and The Guardian newspapers in Nigeria in terms of frequency of coverage in comparison to other SDGs (developmental news).
2. To examine the prominence given to development issues specifically (SDGs) Goals I-IV as compared to other SDGs reported by *Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers
3. To find the direction of coverage given to Sustainable Development Goals I-IV by the *Daily Trust* *Guardian* newspapers.
4. To examine the major sources of news stories (either from the government's ministerial agencies, Civil Society Groups, Community Based Organisations, International Development Partners, or Private Donors or any other sources to which SDGs I-IV were reported by the *Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers.
5. To determine the journalistic genres used by the two newspapers (*Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers) in the coverage of SDG I-IV.

1.5 Research Questions

The study is intended to provide answers to the following research question:

1. To what extent do newspapers (*Daily Trust* and *The Guardian*) cover Sustainable Development Goals SDGs (I-IV) programme in Nigeria in terms of frequency of coverage in relations to other development (Other SDGs)?
2. What is the level of prominence given to development issues specifically SDGs programmes goals I-IV in comparison to other SDGs by the *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* newspapers?
3. What is the direction of coverage *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* cover SDGs programmes specifically Goals I-IV in Nigeria?

4. What are the major sources of news used in the coverage of SDG I-IV by the *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* newspaper? Newspapers in the coverage of SDGs I-IV?
5. In what patterns were journalistic genres used by the *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* newspapers in the coverage of SDGs I-IV?

1.6 Significance of the Study

Being one of the studies in the direction of development communication it is expected that, the study will provoke further critical studies into this pertinent field. However, the study is limited to its scope, it is an assumption that the study will add to the literature to the ongoing global development programme of Sustainable Development Goals in particular and development journalism at large.

The outcome of the study is expected to draw the attention of the Nigerian press towards their major constitutional role of bringing developmental issues as a key priority and keeping the government accountable to the promises they suppose to fulfil.

The study might also be used as a reference point for effective and successful implementation of the SDG programme in Nigeria, and also for further inquiries into this imperative field of media-government relationship. Moreover, the outcome of this study is expected to draw the attention of the press or journalists in Nigeria in the rendering their socio-economic and political functions as the fourth estate of the realm.

1.7 Scope and Limitation of the Study

The scope of this study comprised all issues of the newspapers published in Nigeria between January to December, 2016. The selection of this period is because SDGs took effect on 1st January, 2016 and the Nigerian government adopted the implementation of SDGs in the same year of 2016, within the same year the government is taking both strategic and institutional processes to successful transition from MDGs to SDGs. However, for convenience, the study

limits itself to the coverage and analysis of two Nigerian daily newspapers that is, *Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers.

1.8 Operational Definition of Terms

- Media within the context of the study it refers to a universal tool that serves as a mean of channeling communication for development..
- Press: this specifically means print media of communication aspect, in the course of this study, the press in Nigeria refers to *Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers.
- Coverage: This means journalistic reportage of news stories, editorials, and feature articles/opinions and news analysis of the selected newspapers as they concern SDGs goals I-V which is the focus of this research.
- Newspapers: it means the two sampled newspapers under study i.e *Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers.
- Development news: means any information that is related to poverty, hunger, health and education within the context of the study.

CHAPTER TWO: LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Development Communication: An overview

Development Communication is the type of journalism that pays attention to coverage of ideas, policies, programmes, activities and events dealing with the improvement of lives of people (Edeani, 1993) the term development communication was first coined in the 1960s at the press foundation of Asia. Two Filipino journalists Alan Chalkley and Juan Mercado had a concern about how news organisations superficially covered socio-economic development, while journalists reported government press releases leaving little space for analysis or evolution of development projects today development looks at condition in developing states and how to improve them. It exposes poverty worldwide and helps to research the cause, consequences, and how to address poverty in developing nations. Accordingly, it is the journalist's duty to critically examine and evaluate the relevance of a development project to national and local needs. The difference between a planned scheme and its actual implementation, and the difference between its impacts on the people's claimed by government officials and as it is actually (Aggarwala, 1979). The reporting in national and international events is desirable if they constructively contribute to the development and improvement of the living standard. (Kunazik, 1995).

Different forms of development communication can be identified in the literature (Kunazik, 1995). The first form is comparable to a western-style investigative journalism. It consists of reporting which critically examines development projects on the one hand and controls government activities it further focuses on the conditions in the developing world and how to improve them however, press freedom would be a basic requirement for it. Another form of development journalism is the benevolent- Authoritarian, this allows systematic

manipulation of information in favour of subtle development serving the common welfare. The first type of development communication attempts to document the conditions within remote areas, the internet, with the citizens of the country and report back (Joseph, 2002). On the other side, government participation in mass media can help get important information spread throughout the nation. Government can help to educate their citizens and enlist cooperation in major development projects. However, a government can also use the idea of “developing” the nation in question and therefore citizens are not being given access to the whole pictures (McQuail, 2006).

More recent conceptions include the Chinese version which focuses on intellectual development communication. This stipulates that “the journalists should form a kind of free intelligence and should critically examine the aims of national development and applicable instruments in rational discourse and solve them by reasonable criteria free of social constraints (Kunazik, 1988, p.270; Joseph, 2002)

Development news should critically examine, evaluate and interpret the relevance of development plans, projects, policies, problems and issues. It should indicate the disparities between plans and actual accomplishments and include comparisons with how development is progress in other countries and regions. It should also provide the development process, discuss the impact of plans, projects, policies and issues on people and speculate about the future of development. Development news should refer to the needs of the people which may vary from country to country or from region to region but generally include primary energy sources and electricity, tertiary need such as cultural diversity, recognition and dignity (Aggarwala, Herman Shaw, 1990, p.1035-36 cited in Simiyu, 2015).

2.2 Development, Media and SDGs

It is now a consensus among the scholars of development and communication that communication constitutes a crucial factor in the process of national development. Scholars like Rogers, Lerner Pye, and Schramm has this assertion that among the six circle variables of development, developmental information in the mass media (press) is the most of all (Kadiri, Muhammad, Raji, & Sulaiman (2015). These scholars saw communication and mass media in different ways as independent variables and causal agents in the game of development. Therefore, all over the world the news media or the mass media have been assigned pivotal role in national development.

Schramm and Lerner (1967) are of the view that information or communication occupies an important role in the initial development of third world countries. They believe that the mass media could better the lives of people by supplementing the information resources and exposing them to learning opportunities. Schramm (1964) particularly conceptualized a relationship between development communication and economic growth which has been the main paradigm for development programmes. He observes that when economic activity spreads, knowledge would automatically be gathered more broadly, and information would be widely shared and transferred in the fastest way. This invariably means the development of most of the nations depends on the role communications plays in spreading knowledge, gathering and sharing information.

Rogers (1976), posits that there are three different kinds of tasks for communication to effect social change for development. He observes that “communication provides information about the need for change method and also the benefits of adopting new ways of doing things, secondly; it engineers acceptance of change and thirdly, communication plays an essential role in teaching the new skills necessary for accepted change to be successful.” (P. 58).

Broadcasting media, radio in particular have been adjudged to be the most potent in development communication efforts (Moemeka, 1991). Yet the print media have their advantage. Meomeka notes that the print media have an enduring characteristic distinct from the broadcast media. He further stated that the newspaper can be read at convenience time thus allowing a better understanding of the content message. The newspaper according to him can be stored away for future use, thus making/allowing for the preservation of materials that are considered important for future reference.

In essence, the role of the mass media should be to ensure popular acceptance of goals and implementation strategies of the development programmes. Mass media should be task spaced out with specific communication tasks mapped out for every stage. These tasks according to Obasanjo and Mabogunje (1991) should include creating awareness of the people's interest in the various programmes and projects, stimulating the desire to participate in planning and execution of those programmes and obtaining feedback from the people as their thoughts and conception of those programmes.

Communication is regarded by Obasanjo & Mabogunje (1991) as another interactive process involving impacting of ideas, information values, knowledge, and feelings and so on within a given society. Communication, according to this definition, can thus be seen as a fundamental social process covering vast areas of human interaction. Communication media are expected to set agenda for positive and enduring change by focusing public attention on the need for such changes and for better and more productive ways of doing things via their agenda-setting power, the media have the potential to raise the developmental consciousness of the people and galvanize them towards the consideration of development projects and programmes.

Following the popular remark by Cohen (1963, p.13), it can be used to support the assertion. “The news media might not be successful in telling people what to think but it is stunningly successful in telling its readers what to think about”. Thus, by drawing public attention to change which is what development is often, the people can be prepared for making the necessary transformation efforts.

MacBride et. al. (1980, p.108) also agree with this fact when presupposes that “communication should pursue three aims: increasing understanding of development problems, build up a spirit of solidarity in a common effort and enlarge the capacity of men and women to take charge of their development.” It is believed that communication can be employed not to only inform and educate the people but also to mobilize them to participate effectively in the development process. The media ought to report more systematically as expressed by Piyasoma (1980, p.164) “the gradual transformation of the village from backwards to a progressive community, the emergence of imaginative rural leaders, the efforts exerted by masses of people to build community projects” cited in (Kadiri, Muhammad, Raji,. & Sulaiman, 2015).

The SDGs came into effect in January, 2016 and it is a United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) policy guideline and funding programme for the next fifteen years. The goals are to be accomplished by all member nations (189 countries) by 2030. The Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) also known as the Global Goals (CGs) are structured to end poverty, protect the environment and ensure that all people enjoy peace and prosperity. The goals, 17 in number are fashioned out from the earlier Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and the latter is built upon the successes achieved from the former, also widen the scope of the programme to include other unattended aspects of the MDGs. Below is the summary of the SDGs targets as enunciated by Alamu (2017):

1. Universal plan and agenda to tackle some of the pressing challenges facing the world such as poverty, climate change and conflict. Poverty is at the centre of all these goals.
2. Provide the expertise to drive progress and help support countries on the path to Sustainable Development.
3. Build on the accelerated progress already achieved under the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).

The media is considered as one important pillar for the successful implementation and operationalisation of SDGs both nationally and internationally. In Nigeria, looking at the enormous amount of institutional, political, social and economic change needed to transit from the MDGs to the SDGs. Some key areas of focus have been identified as crucial to the successful take-off of the new goals. These essentially are the strategies that have to be implemented to ensure effective implementation of SDGs in Nigeria a transition strategy has been introduced for successful take-off of the programme. A good number of the transition actions that appear below are interrelated. Therefore, they will need to be considered holistically at the point of implementation.

These thematic areas include institutional framework, Policy and Legal framework, partnership framework, Data Monitoring and Evaluation, Human Resources framework, Communication framework and Financing framework. The communication framework which is vital to the successful take-off of SDGs encompasses the following:

1. Strengthen and reposition the communication/press units of the SDGs PMU (Project Management Unit).
2. Develop countryside and sectoral strategic communication blueprint and use appropriate communication materials to support strategy.
3. Develop appropriate branding for the SDGs.

4. Develop ICT- based communication platform.
5. Strengthen relations between the government and all other stakeholders.
6. Develop a communication strategy for Partnership Framework.
7. Carry out advocacy and sensitization of stakeholders in respect of the SDGs:
 - (a) Private Sector
 - (b) Communities and traditional leaders (Nigeria Transition to SDGs, 2015, p.7)

2.3 Role of Media in Development Communication

The important role communication plays is not just passing on information from one point to another, it is often used as a tool to facilitate and stimulate people participation in development tasks or activities. Such form of communication is known as development communication. Rogers Everett described communication development as the means of facilitating development gain it can thus be describes as an approach to communication which provides communities with information useful for the betterment of their lives. It is the means of sharing Information and experience to accelerate development. Communication also refers to the use of different types of messages designed to transform the behavior of people to participate in development process. More so, different forms of media such as print, electronics, media (radio and television), new media and the like, these media are employed to effectively share knowledge and information to people for developmental purpose. The content of the message is designed (Choudhury, 2011).

The media with specific reference to collective entity of newspapers, radio, television and internet, are important in shaping the development process of a particular country. Development “involves changes or advancement in a nation aimed at improving the political, economic, and social lives of the people” (Melkote & Steevs, 2001). It is a multidimensional process of action, organization and communication and revolves around three factors that

include; economic, political, and cultural spheres of societies. The real influence of the media in national development will depend on the media themselves, the societies in which they operate, and the audience they reach depending on a particular country, varying condition, and a given time. The media influence in dictatorship, for instance, might likely function differently with those in democratic societies. The media's crucial role is overwhelmingly necessary to national development. The media set public agenda and act as the gatekeepers of public issues, they equally perform the watchdog role especially in political transparency, and fight against corruption. As the fourth estate of the realm, the media provides the checks and balances in relation to the three branches of government, as constitutionally provisioned in Nigerian constitution. Media are particularly, important in facilitating nation- building especially of post- colonial societies and those experiencing ethnic and religious diversities. (Melkote & Steeve, 2001).

Media in developing and under developed countries strive to bring in developmental changes, through its message content. Mass media through interpretation, analysis, and discussion point out the draw backs of the society and identify the core areas of development. The message should be such that should create and agitate for change; the message is designed to function as decision maker and teacher.

In Nigeria, while it is evident that mass media contributes immensely to national development of the country particularly; traditional media has made enormous efforts in propagating development agenda since the colonial era, for instance, Kano in northern part of the country had witnessed the usage of cinema popularly known as *Majigi* around 1938 when colonial masters used the medium to create awareness campaign and stimulate peoples participation on health related matters and modern agricultural technology this according to Adamu, Adamu, & Jibril, (2004).

“Was part of a much wider effort to use media and education to create a new sort of modern Hausa citizen. The screening was organized by the health officer, as were many of the early screenings in the north as colonial films were aimed at introducing new modes of health and hygiene, at introducing new agricultural techniques”. (p. 47)

Majigi exhibition were often documentaries about health and farming mixed with entertainment, sports and newsreels. The impetus of colonial film exhibition by the British Imperialists was to curtailed the widely circulated foreign commercial “white” films overwhelmingly American that were considered as disruptive to Hausa cultural heritage. The then Governor of Northern Nigeria during the Colonial Empire, Hesketh Bell, described it as “calculated to have a shocking and dangerous effect on coloured youth” cited in Adamu, Adamu, & Jibril (2004, P.47) hence, the reason for the introduction of educational film in form of Health Propaganda Campaign exhibited in Northern part of Nigeria.

Newspapers’ contribution to the struggle for Nigerian independence is enormous politically; press has contributed immensely to national struggles. Most of the early newspapers owners were nationalists who used their newspapers to advance the course of independence, newspapers like *West African Pilot*, *Eastern Guardian*, *National Spokesman*, and *Southern Nigeria Defender* all owned to Dr. Nmandi Azikwe, had made a tremendous efforts in highlighting and enlightening the public about the need for independence through the content of their publications. In addition, *African Messenger*, a newspaper owned by a prominent journalist, Ernest Ikoli, has contributed to the struggle of independence. (Nwabuezu, 2022).

Newspapers’ contribution to educational development is enormous, newspapers encouraged public to read, *Iwe Irohin*, the first newspaper established in 1859 owned by Rev. Henry Townsend, was primarily established to raise literacy level of Egba community (Nwabueze, 2022). Newspapers content promote the need for western education by encouraging people to seek for education.

In the same vein, radio programmes help to educate people about different socio- economic issues like farming, agriculture, health, small scale industry, and so on. Daniel Lerner while discussing the role of radio as a medium of mass communication and a tool of fostering development issues narrated that the emergence of radio in different villages and town not only help in educating people but bring in consumerism to local communities, the zeal and great desire to own a radio led to good working hard and consequently usher in better standard of living. Radio forums are good weapon for radio producers to involve people in developmental projects. Meanwhile, Televisions as a mass medium has a huge appeal to common person that is why television is planned to motivate people to participate in developmental programmes, media contents such as features, documentaries or development campaign are designed to create interest in the mind of the viewers, contents should be capable of influencing viewers to take part in development programmes. (Choudhury, 2011). The post independence roles of media to Nigerian development involve safeguarding and fostering democratic process, especially through their watch dog role. They have been playing a major role in development process and stimulate change action through the channels of communications both in educational, human, political, economic, social aspects of development. They are fostering rural and urban development through the techniques of communication development, mobilizing the public to participate in development tasks and projects.

2.4 Review of Related Literature

A lot of research has been conducted both from economists' point of view, sociologists, educationists, as well as communication perspective. From the economists' point of view, there was a study conducted on the *Prospects for Achieving Sustainable Development Goals through the Millennium Development Goals in Nigeria* by Adejuma and Adejumo (2014) the

study focus was to examine the analytical concept of sustainable development as it affects the economic growth of Nigeria. The findings of the study indicate that the issue of sustainability must be a concern to all parastatals both (private and public sectors) and individuals, this will require educating everyone on the need for sustainable development hence walk towards the actualization of the development programme and projects as well.

The study provides some factors that serve as an obstacle to achieving sustainable development in the Less Economically Developed Countries (LEDCs) these include among others, the priorities of LEDCs government and individuals are often short term, meaning in meeting the basic needs of the population corruptions made it difficult to prioritize long term issues in the sense that, many leaders are in office for short periods and are frequently changing; lack of qualified people to develop and implement alternative technologies due to a poor educational system; lack of education about finite resources. People do not understand the implication of overuse resources. In the light of these challenges, specific development effects have to be employed that encompasses Environmental Protection; Economic Development and Social Development. The research suggested the governing bodies promote policies that will lead to the sustainability of development programmes such as SDGs; these policies should invariably be inconsistent with international policies for the achievement of the overall global sustainable development.

A related study on the same field of the economy was done by Dansabo, (2017). The study looks at the progress so far made in Nigeria through SD goals and the findings of the study reveals that the area where Nigeria did well according to the reports made available in 2016 is global partnership for development, the country is actively participating in a number of regional initiatives such as African Union (AU), and the new Partnership for African Development (NEPAD). The country also belongs to several bilateral and multilateral trade

pacts such as the World Trade Organization (WTO), the Economic Community of West African Countries (ECOWAS) and African Caribbean Pacific- European economic partnership (ACP -EU-EPA).

When looking at the performance of MDGs in Nigeria in the study, conflicting reports have been identified, while its obvious UNDP (2007) report highlighted in some of the successes of the former MDGs, the country was slow in some goals particularly goals 1 (poverty and hunger) and 6 (combat HIV, Malaria, Tuberculosis and other communal diseases) the situation is worse in Goals 4 (reduce child mortality), 5 (improve maternal health), and 7 (ensure environmental sustainability) while a remarkable achievement has been gained in goal 8 (global partnership for development) as earlier stated. However, the Nigerian Government on its part has a contrary report. According to the Director of Programme in the office of the Special Assistant to the President on MDGs, Nigeria recorded major progress in the MDGs. With reference to Goal II, he stated that primary six completion rate has improved from 74% in 2012 to 82% in 2014 likewise gender parity there was also a significant improvement in goal 4 from a figure of 157 under-five deaths per 1,000 death live birth to 89 per 1000 death in 2014 similarly, the infant mortality rate of 61% per 1000 live births declined to 58 in 2014. The same with Maternal Mortality Rate (MMR) was estimated as 1000 per 100,000 in 1990 goal 6 received remarkable progress of 5.8 to 3.4 in 2014 despite the stated progress Nigeria was slow in meeting the MDGs which need to calls for explanation.

The findings of the study indicate that although varying reports existed on the performance of MDGs both from International bodies like UNDP and the Nigeria federal government, both reports were not encouraging, the study expatiates that, lessons learnt from the previous MDGs will lead to a successful implementation of the current SDG programme in the country.

More so, the outcome of the study reveals that the 17 SDGs are all-encompassing that include all the vital aspects of human beings, the realization of the goals in developing societies may prove to be relatively difficult due to the absence of basic infrastructure like railway, roads, information technologies, sanitation, electric power and water remain scarce in most of developing nations Nigeria inclusive.

Malaolu, & Ogbuabor, (2017) in a study *Towards Achieving Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria: Role of CSOs and VOPEs* presupposes the Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) are influencers and supporters of SDGs among the functions they include: broad networks to engage in an awareness campaign and sensitization of the general public on SDGs, CSOs also strengthen and leverage the impacts of development programmes by providing local knowledge, identifying potential risks, targeting assistance and expanding reach, particularly at the community level, they can also promote public consensus and local ownership for reforms and reduction in national poverty and development strategies through the creation of knowledge sharing networks and building common ground for understanding. Besides, Voluntary Organizations Professional Evaluators (VOPEs) can also serve as a training platform by supporting appropriate training and capacity building programmes needed to deliver staff and other stakeholders to enhance their productivity and efficiency in implementing SDGs programmes and projects.

Lawrence (2018) conducted a similar study on the *performance achieved from SDGs in Nigeria*, the study highlighted some of the factors that hinder the progress of MDGs implementation in Nigeria from 2000-2015 these factors among others include unmanageable population; pervasive poverty within the inhabitants of Nigeria; ignorance and superstition due to the lack of adequate quality among the citizens; religious dogmatism in the northern part of the country; ethnic conflicts in the middle belt like herders – farmers

clashes, corruption and economic mismanagement and so on. Education has a powerful role in the implementation of SD goals, as reveals in the study there is a need for every Nigerian state to have a sustainable development body that will monitor agencies, organizations and ministries contributing to achieving SDGs. The Nigerian state needs to target providing quality education to children through curriculum improvement and fund research for the advancement of society's development. The study also highlights the necessity of the relevant stakeholder to educate the general population through community awareness campaigns all over the nation for people to understand why they must protect their environment, livelihood and also health.

Looking at the educationist point of view, a study was conducted by Alamu (2017) titled *Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria: What role(s) for Nigeria's Indigenous Languages* the study stated the roles linguists, language expert and stakeholders in promoting and developing indigenous languages were paramount of importance, for Nigeria to successfully take off the post-2015 agenda before 2030, the level of illiteracy must drastically be reduced and our indigenous languages must be incorporated in form of creating public awareness.

In a related development, a study done by the UN System Task Team on the post-2015 UN Development Agenda titled "Review of contributions of the MDG Agenda to foster development: Lessons for the post- 2015 UN Development Agenda" (2012). The study looks at the characteristics of the MDGs and their contribution to global development. MDGs is a simple, transparent and easy to communicate agenda and provided the basis for converging advocacy. MDGs have received an unprecedented political commitment which reflects a strong consensus for tackling poverty reduction and other key priorities.

From the scientific point of view, Jaiyesimi, (2016) presupposes that SDGs Agenda need not only to pay attention to implementing the substantial goals (SDGs I-6) in integrated way, but

also ensuring the means of implementation of goal 17 and the other goals are themselves an integrated undertaking. The defining challenge of this era according to the study is to accelerate development that is economically sound, socially inclusive and environmentally sustainable.

The Sustainable Development Goals embody nothing less than to represent the best possible opportunity of all the complexities of the current confrontations of economic development.

The looming challenges in Africa as discovered from the study are wide and deep and will require an innovative response that is embedded in partnership and rooted in our shared values of justice, fairness, equity and solidarity. The time is now to ensure that Africa is not left behind in achieving the SDGs and the beneficiaries of this will be Africans and the people of the world at large. The measure of our success in implementing the sustainable development goals in Africa will be the attainment of the components of the 17 Goals by 2030. It can be done provided the key factors imports for successful implementation of SDGs, factors such as; high level of political support, ownership by the countries, institutional and human capacity development, mutual accountability and policy reform are established and sustained. The success of the SDGs in Africa will hinge on a credible means of implementation. From the communication perspective, Onyeizu, & Binta (2014), conducted a research on *Newspaper Coverage of Health Issues in Nigeria (A study of the Guardian and Punch Newspapers January 2010 to December, 2011)*. The researchers analyze the role of media have in communicating development messages, two newspapers were content analyzed that is *Guardian* and *Punch* for 24 months and a total of 554 health reports out of 208 editions of the newspapers sampled were collected and analyzed. The outcome of the study reveals that newspapers do not give prominence to health issues by way of placement and allocation of space, instead of some other controversial issues such as politics, crime economy were

highlighted most. The findings also indicate HIV/ AIDS as the most emphasized health issue which means it was the greatest health problems during the period under study. It was also discovered that majority of the stories were in straight news format meaning that, the newspapers did not give enough analysis of health issues but did more on the information basis. For this reason, the study suggested for newspapers to give adequate attention to development issues, more importantly, other health-related issues that are enlisted in both the former MDGs and current SDGs agenda.

It was also recommended for health reporters to liaise with the health professionals and medical researchers for an effective understanding of the health-related matters that enable them to internalize the reports and simplify them for public consumption. Furthermore, with a comprehensive grasp of the information one gets on health-related issues, a reporter can package it in simple language by breaking down the scientific jargons without distorting the actual meaning. At last, the media were suggested to publish more features or news analysis and editorials and not just straight news. The government should also provide an enabling environment for the media to perform by providing them with the necessary information as required.

Another perspective from media and communication aspect is the work of Wole -Abu (2018) in a study *The Role of Traditional Media in the Propagation of the Sustainable Development Goals in Nigeria*, the study posits that sustainable development goals will be achieved if the traditional media make information and news as its focal point especially among the people in rural areas. This assertion was supported by Wainwright (1982) claim as cited in the study, journalism is information processed to cater to the human curiosity of a world that also wants to be aware of what is happening now. Media reports which are gathered systematically are aired or published to people to enable them to prepare, act or react to what is happening

around them and event in the world. The media especially traditional media have the power to mobilize people and spur them to action. The study emphasized the essential key functions of the media as to inform, educate and entertain.

In a related study on Millennium Development Goals titled *Reporting MDGs in the Nigerian Press: Analysis of Universal Basic Education (Goal II) Coverage by Guardian and Daily Trust Newspapers from 2001-2015* by Alkali (2011) the work content analysed a total of 608 editions of the two said newspapers for five years and the findings of the study reveals that the two sampled newspapers gave less coverage to the Millennium Development Goals within the period of the study. The coverage of goal II (UBE) under MDGs was not given much prominence due to the fact that *Daily Trust* accorded 1.6% to UBE issues on the front page and none was recorded in the *Guardian* newspapers. More so there is much difference between the *Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers in the coverage of Goal II of the MDGs as both papers accorded less coverage of the UBE issues in their respective newspapers. The cause of less coverage of MDG Goal II as the outcome of the study revealed is due to the lack of commitment from the part of the Federal Government of Nigeria to have total ownership of the development programmes as contained in the Millennium Declaration. The study also shows that even though the Nigerian press is devised and often reflected the diverse plurality of interest in the coverage of development issues, little attention was paid to the MDGs as the study findings revealed.

In his study Bello (2015), Titled *Newspaper Coverage of Health Issues in Nigeria: the frequency of reporting Malaria, HIV/AIDS and Polio and the effect of seeking health information on the health behaviours of newspaper readers*. The study employed a mixed method of research design by adopting both qualitative and quantitative methods. However, 844 editions of the four sampled newspapers were content analyzed to get the frequency of the coverage of

health-related matters by the newspapers while 13 health reporters from different newspaper publishers were interviewed to get in-depth information. The study measures the relationship and statistical correlation between health coverage in Nigerian newspapers and several other variables. These include malaria, HIV/AIDS, and polio in Nigeria especially in the north, and the health behaviours of Nigerian newspaper readers. Furthermore, the study measures the relationship between global health campaigns such as [Global Malaria Action for HIV/AIDS (2012-2015) by the World Health Organization, Global Health Action (2005-2006) by the collaboration of public health experts, non-governmental organizations, civil society activists and so on] and the newspaper coverage of malaria, HIV/AIDS and polio in the Nigerian newspapers to determine the influence of global health in the coverage of these health problems in Nigeria. The study also examines the relationship between health reporting and the influence or effects of health and science training among health reporters to determine the challenge involved in newspaper health reporting in Nigeria and this underpins the agenda-setting facet of the study. It was discovered that without the ongoing global health campaigns, the consequences of endemic diseases would likely be much worse in Nigeria and many other developing countries across the world. Among the key findings of the study was that newspapers in all societies remain veritable means of informing people and creating awareness about health issues. This further confirms the resourceful value noted of newspapers since their emergence in the 17th century as enunciated by George, Curran, & Wintage, 1978; Tom 2012; J. Weber, 2006 cited in the study and still in the 21st century it was asserted based on the findings of the study that newspapers are still important to members of the public in obtaining Health information to improve their health. Furthermore, newspapers may still be noted as one of the leading media channels that promote health information on various health issues for the benefit of society.

In a related development, a study by Kelleher, (2014) was done on *A Consideration of Development Journalism in the Context of Rwandan Newspapers, 2013*, the study examines the development news content of two Rwandan newspapers (The *New Times* and *ImvahoNshya* newspapers, in an attempt to tease out the theoretical bases upon which development journalism in Rwanda is applied in practice, and the historical and political dictates that influence that practice, and also to gain insight into the vocational imperatives of Rwandan journalists and the print news media. The study discovered that national economic development was a focus of journalism practice in Rwanda, but the development journalism model represented in the *News Times* and *ImvahoNshya* newspapers exhibited more traditional journalism practice than 21st-century development communication theory.

The outcome of the study has shown how development journalism was found to be an active and engaged model in 2013 in the Rwandan newspapers but detailed examination revealed significant weaknesses in the model's implementation remarkably, the government's pro-poor representation. The result of the study was considered in the context of two significant, alternatively reinforcing and contradictory historical legacies: Colonialism and the 1994 Genocide against the Tutsi. German and Belgian colonizers asserted economic development in an authoritarian modernization paradigm implemented via strategies that pitted indigenous society against itself, Rwandans have historical reasons to distrust development processes. With political independence in Rwanda came magnified ethnic conflict, and with independent press came hate media; Rwandans have no successful experience with or expectations for a free press. Rwandan society has reason to be wary of authority, but also fearful of unfettered participation.

The study indicates that government and media representatives in Rwanda have considered journalism to be a significant part of the success of national development plans, echoing

assertions by journalism and development communication scholars. The theoretical bases for development journalism have focused on the legitimacy of goals—modernization through open markets, national control to overcome dependency, or democratic participation—and effectiveness of outcomes. Rwanda’s national experience of colonialism, extreme conflict, Underdevelopment and emerging stability provide an important historical, cultural, and economic context to better understand those theories of development communication and their real-world application in development journalism.

Another study by Yusha’u (2014) on *Nigerian Newspapers and the Coverage of Development Issues: An analysis of This day and Daily Trust Newspapers* was conducted in the field of Media and Communication the study was aimed at investigating the role of development news on the two sampled newspapers making a comparative analysis. The study employed both quantitative methods of research design that is content analysis and qualitative method of in-depth interview to arrive at a conclusion. The study covers a time frame of one year using *This day* and *Daily Trust* as a case study and a total of 104 editions of the manifest contents of the newspapers understudy was analyzed. The findings of the study were categorized into two: findings from the content of the newspapers and the field of an interview conducted.

From *This day* newspaper, the findings indicate a total coverage of 5,499 development issues recorded 295 which represent 5% equivalent to 5.41% of the newspaper total coverage while non- development matters constituted 95% which is equivalent to 94.58% of 5,154 of the total non-development coverage by the newspaper. This clearly shows how development matters are under covered by *This day* newspaper this implies that people are not expected to be well informed and educated in terms of development issues.

The same newspaper in the area of health recorded 108 appearance represented by 37% equivalent to 36.61% of the total newspaper coverage which means that it is averagely

represented within the sphere of development issues. Agriculture accorded 37, to represent 12% (12.54%) that is the least, education recorded 150 which constituted 51% (50.84%) of the total development issues. According to the study findings education matters also receives an average priority against other development issues like agriculture.

From the *Daily Trust* newspaper investigation, the findings indicate a higher figure when compared to *This day* newspaper with a total coverage volume of 6,166 out of which 476 coverage came from development aspect representing 8% equivalent to 7.71% while 5,699 volume of coverage was recorded from non-development issues representing 92% equivalent to 92.28% of the total coverage. Analysis shows that development issues are generally not adequately covered. From the breakdown, health recorded 179 frequency of appearance represented by 36% (35.71%). Agriculture recorded 63 which is 13% (13.23%) the least in the record is education with 243 figure represented by 51% equivalent to 51.05% of the total coverage.

The study findings from the qualitative design, that is in-depth interview section, it was discovered that development issues in *This day* newspaper are not covered adequately and the reporters lack effective training in reporting development issues which by implication would negatively affect the performance of their duty especially when it comes to investigative reporting on development issues. The study findings also revealed how imperative editors have in determining the content of the newspaper despite reporters' role in sourcing the news items from the field. The training should also be extended to editors. With regards to prominence, development matters sometimes do covers the front page of the *This day* newspaper nonetheless, positioning of the story on the front page may not be strategic to readily capture the attention of the readers as the study revealed. What we observed daily is the caption of political stories covering the front page of newspapers.

Because newspaper ownership has a great influence on the contents of the newspapers products. It was also part of the study findings discovery on how editorial policies dictate the content of newspapers publications.

Gefechu (2017) researched *The Practice of Development Journalism on TV Oromiya: 'Iftoomaa' in focus* the general objective of the study was to examine the practice of development journalism on TV Orumiya centering on 'Iftoomaa' Programme as a case study. 'Iftoomaa' Programme provides a platform to officials to explain some decisions deemed against the interest of the public or controversial, the programme is highly relied on investigative journalism which involves exposing public matters that are concealed either deliberately by someone in a position of power or due to inefficiency. 'Iftoomaa' Programme also was intended to clarify the public figures about various development activities planned and done by regional government bodies (legislative, executive and judiciary). As the programme is designed to defend the public interest through exposing wrongdoings and corruption, it discloses a lack of good governance, abuses of power and maladministration so that government would take corrective measures it assumed that the public will be aware of the effects of poor governance and stand to defend its right.

The study employed a mixed method of quantitative and qualitative research designs. Therefore, content analysis was adopted to review the 'Iftoomaa' programme on TV Oromiya's development journalism practices, the researcher employed content analysis to find out whether the content of (Iftoomaa) programme has been developed in line with the notion of development journalism. The study uses this tool to specifically find out whether the 'Iftoomaa' programme in focus does what it intends to do that is investigative journalism. The qualitative aspect involves the use of the in-depth interview to gather essential information that assists to answer the research questions of the study. Accordingly, the study

also conducts interview with professionals (reporters, editors, and producers) who are directly or indirectly taking a part in producing the 'Iftoomaa' programme to gather their opinion about the programme.

The research conducted, used the theoretical foundation of development journalism and found that the practice of development journalism in the medium has a good beginning. As evident in the study, the deep renewal process has begun at federal and regional levels and it was part of renewal process, the Oromiya regional government has reformed the management of the medium; the director-general of the organization and the board of directors of TVO has been replaced. The newly appointed board members have played a significant role in improving the context of TV Oromiya by motivating the journalists to expand the experiences of the success stories and expose wrongdoings in government offices based on editorial policy, rules and regulations of the country and their professional ethics.

The findings also indicate the high dedication of 'Iftoomaa' programme produced in exercising their social responsibility, they committed themselves to defend the right of citizens and thereby improved the living standard of peoples by enduring accountability of public officials. The findings revealed all the contents of the selected 'Iftoomaa' programme as having the promising effect of the producers in framing the citizens as the subject of development projects and highlighting the impacts of youth unemployment, land grab, corruption, and poor governance on the social, political and economic activities of the region.

In essence, the overall assessment shows the effective practice of development journalism in TVO and the 'Iftoomaa' programme in particular despite its young age as contained in the study therefore, the television development programme is on its right track of the model of development journalism. The effect of development journalists working in the medium to promote the socio-economic development of the region and expose maladministration which

is affecting the society is of paramount importance to fly high development journalism in Ethiopian country.

2.5. Theoretical Framework

2.5.1 Agenda Setting Theory

This study is supported by the Agenda Setting Theory of McCombs and Shaw, (1977). The basic premise of the theory is how news media reports on particular issues, can influence or shapes public awareness and debate, editors' act as gatekeepers of mass-mediated messages. They can provide sustained and prominent coverage to an issue while others marginalised or ignored.

The beginning of Agenda Setting Theory can be traced as far back as 1922 when Walter LippMann expresses his concern on the vital role that mass media can do in influencing the setting of certain images on the public mind in trying to demonstrate the influence of mass media, Lipmann exemplifies with those individuals who supposed to be enemies, while their countries are at war. Instead of becoming enemies, without having access to information about the war through media, those individuals are able to live harmoniously in a secluded island (Lippmann, 1922). Lippmann indicates on how mass media can set a particular agenda which can influence the opinion of the public. So he did generate the foundation for the Agenda Setting Theory.

Taking clue from Lippmann, in 1963, Bernard Cohen, observed that while media do not tell us what to think, they might tell us what to think about. This suggests that mass media has the potential to draw the people's attention to certain issues, and allow for a conclusion already raised in the public still maintaining the individual members of society reflect such issues already raised, and then cut make personal submissions based on their subjective reasons (Cohen, 1963).

Agenda Setting Theory describes the ability of the news media to influence the important topic of the public agenda, it attempts to influence viewers, and establish a hierarchy of news prevalence. Agenda setting is the creation of public awareness and concern of secret issues of the news media. Two basic assumptions that underline most researches on agenda-setting include; the press and the media do not reflect reality they filter and shape it and secondly, the media concentration on a few issues and subjects leads the public to perceive those issues as more important than other issues. McComb and Shaw, 1972).

2.5.1.2 Types of Agenda Setting

The research on the effect of Agenda Setting compares the science of issues in news content with the public perception of the most important issue, and then analyse the extent of influence of the media. There are three models assumed by McComb (1972): The awareness model, The Priorities model and The Science model.

Most investigations are centered on these three models Rogers and Dearing (1988) identify three types of agenda setting

- (i) Public Agenda setting in which the public agenda is treated as the dependent variables (the traditional hypothesis).
- (ii) Media Agenda setting in which the media agenda is treated as the dependent (agenda building)
- (iii) Policy agenda setting in which elite policy makers agenda are treated as the dependent variables (political agenda setting).

Rogers and Dearing argue that mass media research has focused a great deal on public agenda setting and media agenda setting while largely ignored policy agenda which is studied primarily by political scientists. For this reason, the Rogers & Dearing suggests that mass communication scholars to pay more attention on how media and public agendas might

influence elite's policy makers, the correlation between where policy makers get their news and how this affects their policies.

2.5.1.3 Limitations to Agenda Setting Theory

The continuing debates between the proponents and opponents of Cohen's view on Agenda Setting theory circle around the questions of media influence on how directly and to what degree the media set the public agenda. Some of the recent studies propose that personal variables can mitigate the effects of media agenda setting on an individual or audience. (Matsaganis & Payne; 2005; Gross & Aday, 2003; McComb and Shaw, 1997) cited in (Zain, N. R. 2014)

These majorly contributed from the background education and understanding of the media audience on the issue or agenda which is presented by the mass media (Carter, 1996). Their opinions are more difficult to be influenced by the information that they received from the mass media (Matsaganis & Payne, 2005). Moreover, such influence from the mass media in forming opinion is impossible to those people who lived far away from the information provided or to those who are difficult to get accessibility of the information from the mass media. (Lippmann, 1922).

It was also argued that the way news is presented is entirely different from the way news is received and decoded by the audience there is great possibility of having misinterpretation from the audience. Some of the opponents also argue that the theory is suited to election campaign related news and could not be suited to other types of contents.

2.5.1.4 Relevance of the Theory to the Study

Agenda setting theory is pertinent to this study because of its powerful capacity to draw the audience/ readers attention and influence them towards development issues. In other words, the media are entrusted with the power of setting agenda on issues they consider as

imperative to society. In the same vein, they can set agenda on SDGs and that will become a major issue of public discourse it will also create much-needed attention for the SDGs projects. However, The media can serve as gatekeepers and held the government accountable through constant reporting of development-related issues, analysis of projects undertaken by the governing bodies and regular assessment of the performance and implementation of SDGs programme. Thus, the frequency, prominence and direction of News coverage, features, editorials, and feature articles made by the Nigerian press will have a tremendous effect towards a resolution of daunting development challenges hence could lead to attaining the desired result.

2.5.2. Media Framing Theory

Framing as a concept is closely related to agenda setting but it takes the research further by focusing on the issues at hand. The agenda framing model was propounded by Erving Goffman in 1974, in his book *Framing Analysis: An essay on the organisation of experience*. Goffman's attempt to explain conceptual frames- ways to organise to organise experience – structure an individual's perception of society. The perception is about the organisation of experience rather than the organisation of society. The media tends to draw attention to certain events and situates them within an area that will give meaning. In framing, the media tends to draw attention to certain topics, this stems from the way news is presented, and the frame in which the news is presented mostly is a choice that is made by journalists. Framing is all about the way the media-wise serve as gatekeeper to arrange and present the news and issues they cover and the way the news is received and interpreted by the audience.

In other words, framing theory suggests that how particular issue, event or topic is presented to the audience called “frame” influences the choices people make about how to process that information. Frames are abstractions that work to organise or structure the meaning of the

message. The most common use of frames is in terms of the frame the news or media place on the information they convey. They are thought to influence the perception of the news by the audience, in this way it could be constructed as a form of second level agenda – setting, they not only tell the audience what to think about (agenda-setting theory), but also how to think about that issue (Goffman, 1974).

McQuail (2005, p.379) captures it when he posits that framing consists of using words or phrases, making certain contextual references, choosing certain pictures or films, giving examples as typical referring to certain sources and so on. According to Bleske (1995), the way news is framed has important effects on the way the information in the news is processed. Similarly, Ike (2005, p.88) opines the framing refers to how messages are encoded with meaning so that they can efficiently be interpreted in relation to existing beliefs or ideas. Framing is used to explain how the mass media promote a particular definition of an issue through selection, emphasis, exclusion, and elaboration.

2.5.2.1 Types of Frames

Semetko & Valkenburg (2000) propose five types of frames media often adopt in treating news.

1. Conflict frame: frame here is reduces complex social and political problems into a simple form, with emphasis placed on the performance and style of combatants.
2. Human Interest frame: this places emphasis on the personal and emotional side of an event, issue or problem.
3. Economic consequences frame: the emphasis here is on economic impact or implication of an issue or event for a particular nation. Frame is used to make an event relevant to the public.

4. Mortality frame: the function of this type of frame is to add a religious or moral change to an event; it is often used as in responses by news sources rather than the expressed view of journalists.
5. Responsibility frame: it presents crisis in a such a way that the responsibility for causing it lies with the government, an individual or group.

The theoretical assumption of framing shows that news coverage and presentation is a function of certain knowledge, structure, and socio-cultural maps of journalists (Semetko, & Valkenburg 2000).

2.5.2.2 Limitations to Framing Theory

Baran and Devis (2010 p.335) suggests four weaknesses to framing analysis as follows:

Framing is highly flexible and open-ended in other words it (lacks speciality); it is not able to address presence or absence of effects; it precludes causal explanation because of qualitative method of research and; framing assumes individual make frequent framing errors (question individuals' abilities).

2.5.2.3 Relevance of the Theory to the Study

To be able to play a useful role in the propagation of SDGs, bringing the 17 Goals to the attention of public discourse is the power attached to the media/press. They must frame the news spotted by the people, it becomes necessary to provide the SDGs frame news into a meaningful format that will lead to effective influence in the perception of the news set on the development programmes and projects. Framing takes into consideration factors like selection, exclusion and elaboration as earlier stated (Scheufele & Tewkbury, 2007).

Based on the agenda-setting and media framing theories the study seeks to examine the Nigerian media's contribution to SDG goals. The study will seek to examine whether the press in Nigeria has been raising the SDGs related goals to the public agenda and also if the Nigerian

press performs a watchdog role that is holding the government accountable and committed to SDGs actualisation in.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

This chapter discusses the research procedure followed and provides a clear understanding of how the research was conducted. It explains the research methodology, techniques and instruments used in the process of data collection, sampling techniques adopted, units analysed, contents categorised and the approach used for measurement, presentation and analysing the data collected.

3.1 Research Design

For any research to be practicable and fruitful, it requires a methodology to adopt. For this study, quantitative Content Analysis best serves in line with its peculiarity of looking out for patterns in the manifest content of communication. Content analysis was described by Neunendorf (2002) as “the primary message-centered methodology” (p.9). Also, Cites studies such as that of Riffe and Frietag (1997) and Yale and Gilly (1988) which reported that “in the field of mass communication research content analysis has been the fastest-growing technique over the past 20 years or so” (Neuendorf, 2002, p.1 cited in Macnamara, 2005, p.1). Kimberly Neuendorf a prominent researcher in media content analysis provides this definition “Content Analysis is a summarizing, quantitative analysis of messages that relies on the scientific methods.... And it’s limited as to the types of variables that may be measured or the context in which the messages are created or presented” (Neuendorf 2002, p. 10). Noteworthy about this definition is that she claims media content analysis is quantitative research not qualitative, and she strongly advocates the use of scientific methods including

“attention to objectivity -intersubjectivity, priori design, reliability, validity, generalizability and hypothesis testing” (p.10). For Babbie, (2011, p. 356) “Content analysis is the study of recorded human communications”... Expatiating further, Leedy and Ormrod, (2013,p. 148) clarify “....content analysis is a detailed and systematic examination of the contents of a particular body of material to identify patterns, themes, or biases.”

Jethwaney (2013) identifies the relevance of content analysis in measurement practices and affirms its global use by consultancy firms, media monitoring agencies and companies which they generally relate with as media content analysis particularly in India where it is handled as media content analysis quantitatively. She however argues about certain factors that determine communication outputs: Identifying the target audience/market, earning the attention of those audiences and surpassing the competition.

In the view of Kerlinger, (2000) Content analysis is a method of studying and analyzing communication in a systematic, objective and quantitative manner to measure variables. Content analysis is considered the most appropriate, valuable and reliable method for this research as the manifest contents of the selected papers were quantitatively measured and analyzed using scientific means of collecting, analyzing and interpreting data arriving at a conclusion.

3.2 Universe of the Study

According to Nworgu (1991), what determines the population of the study in organized research is the problem under investigation. The population of this study, therefore, comprises all editions published by the Nigerian Newspapers from January to December 2016 for this study two national newspapers were selected to represent the population of the study. These newspapers are; the *Guardian* and *Daily Trust* amounting to 522 editions for one year were sampled and analysed as explained in the sample size below. According to Ohaja

(2003, p.67), “the idea behind this delimitation of boundaries is to avoid embarking on an unmanageable venture”. The justification for the selection of the *Guardian* newspaper was because; the paper was founded by a group of intellectual teams, mostly from the literacy class. Also, it’s one of the popular newspaper with a good reputation all over the country that is why it gained a wider circulation and readership strength all over the nation (Nnadozie, 2013) in the same vein, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) is a universal development programme that encompasses all the intellectuals bodies in its implementation process, it’s the expectation of the researcher that the paper will give SDG goals a key consideration in terms of coverage of SDGs. *Daily Trust*, on the other hand, is the first daily newspaper from the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The paper is the most popular paper from Northern Nigeria with strong readership circulation, wider coverage of national issues and popularity all over the country.

Moreover, based on the findings of a nationwide All media and Product Survey (AMPS), the paper was rated as the number one newspaper on readership in 2015 according to a report of media facts released in July 2016 (*Daily Trust* Publication, 2016). In essence, the selection of these papers was based on their popularity, wider coverage of national issues and strength of readership circulation as they are among the top ten widely circulated newspapers in Nigeria. The study limits the study on the analysis of editorials, features/opinions, news analysis and news stories that are related to poverty, hunger, health and well being as well as education these represent goals I-IV of SDGs programme, while the analysis of news stories will cover both the SDGs I-IV and other SDGs, this is to have a clear picture and understanding on the emphasis given to SDGs I-IV as compared to other SDGs. However, it is limited to answering RQ1 and RQ2 which involves the analysis of News stories in terms of frequency of occurrence and prominence as expatiates in the units of analysis and content categories defined below.

However, letters to the editor, columnists, interviews, advertisements, cartoons and photographic images are excluded in the course of the study analysis.

3.3 Sample Size

Sample size refers to the members or elements which have been proportionally selected from the study population and on which the actual investigation is carried out. It is a smaller group of elements drawn through a definite procedure from a specified study population. Ohaja (2003, p.75) believes that selecting a sample size “is necessitated by the impracticability of studying the entire population in most cases.”

In the case of this study, the total editions of *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* newspapers from January to December, 2016 formed both the sample size of the study. Furthermore, a total of 522 editions of the two selected newspapers formed the sample size of this study. The procedure for arriving at this sample size was explained in the sampling techniques below.

3.4 Sampling Technique

Two newspapers were purposively selected to form the population of this study. The study employed Census- Total Coverage sampling procedure whereby the entire editions of the selected newspapers was studied and analyzed for a period of twelve (12) months (January to December, 2016). A census study occurs if the entire population is very small or it is reasonable to include the entire population. Furthermore, it is called a census sample because data is gathered from every member of the population. In other words, the method involves studying the entire population or universe of the research. A census which is also systematic is an attempt to gather information about every individual in a population as described by Wimmer and Dominick (2011, p. 87) “the process of examining every member in a population is called a census”. Thus, the results are always presumed as good as explained by Kothari (2004) “it can be presumed that in such inquiry when all items are covered, no element of

chance is left and highest accuracy is obtained” (p. 72). The justification for adopting this sampling technique and the time frame of the study is because, SDGs was adopted in 2015 and launched in January, 2016 and the strategic process for transitioning from MDGs to SDGs in Nigeria started the same year, For example, Nigeria Road map to SDGs was released in October, 2015 meanwhile the SDGs Indicators Baseline was made available in 2016 due to the lack of maximum coverage obtained from the former MDGs. The study emphasized 2016 that was the year the SDGs was launched to examine if the selected newspapers intend to emphasize the current programme against the previous development programme. Meanwhile, because of the limited time frame, a total population coverage will be suitable for the study to enable the researchers to gather enough data to generalize the findings of the study.

In determining the sample size of the study, a 2016 calendar was used; there is a total of 366 days in the year as shown in the table appeared on appendix no. ii (page no.116)

There is total week days of 261 and a total number of weekend days of 105 to give a total number of 366 days in 2016 . Therefore, since the selected newspapers are daily, we have a total of 261 editions in a year for a particular paper multiply by two to have a total of 522 editions for the two newspapers under study. This represents the sample size of the study as mathematically demonstrated below:

$$261 \times 2 = 522,$$

Daily Trust—————261

This Day—————261

Total—————522

3.5 Units of Analysis

According to Wimmer and Dominick (2011, p.164) “unit of analysis is the smallest element of content analysis. In print, units of analysis might be a single word, a theme, a headline etc”.

Therefore, the units of analysis for this study are as follows:

- **News Stories:** This simply implies the conventional news stories as defined and understood in journalism. News stories within the context of this study are the editorial items that report daily events or happening newspapers.
- **Editorials:** it is the official position of what a particular newspaper organization stands for on an issue of public interest. It is the reaction to events and issues of a day and a newspaper contribution to such matters.
- **Feature articles:/Opinions** this could be feature stories or opinions written by either any staff of the newspaper editorial crew as well as the independent writers outside the organization. it goes into great details regarding concepts and deals mainly with the opinion of the writer.
- **News Analysis:** this means an in-depth analysis in the coverage of SDGs I-IV. It could be in form of news writings and reporting. It goes deeper in analysing issues in a more analytical mode.

Units of analysis in this study do not include columnists, interviews, pictures or photographs, letters to the editor, cartoons and advertisements. The Selection of news stories in this research was informed by the fact that it provides a gist or hint right from the lead. Likewise, editorials, features/opinions and news analysis from both the editorial crew and individuals outside the newspaper organizations determine the kind of prominence and attention given to each particular issue on the newspapers under study. The interest in Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) was on Goals I-IV of the said development programme that

includes; fighting against poverty, tackling the rampant issue of hunger, health and well-being issues as well as the issuance of qualitative education in the Nigerian society. To get a clear picture of how the selected newspapers pay attention to the said SDGs I-IV the researcher makes a comparative analysis to know the frequency of coverage and story positioning of other SDGs or (other development) issues in comparison to SDGs I-IV.

Moreover, the units of analysis that appeared on the news pages in the selected newspapers were information about SDGs related to poverty, hunger, health and education these can either be related to government pronouncements about Sustainable Development goals and projects, actual project sites or launching as well as the activities of NGO's being reported by the selected papers.

In a nutshell, the study focused attention on the analysis of news stories in answering the research questions 1 and 2 (that is to know the level of attention given to SDG goals I- IV in terms of frequency of occurrence and prominence given to the said categorized units analysed in comparison to other SDGs). The editorials, feature articles/opinions, news analysis and news stories were analyzed in the course of answering research questions 3, which examines the direction in which Sustainable Development Goal I-IV were covered, meanwhile, all the four units of analysis (news stories, editorials, feature articles/opinions and news analysis) were also assessed in investigating the actors or major players in the coverage of SDGs I-IV and also have a clear picture on the journalistic genres used in the coverage of SDGs I-IV by the two sampled newspapers in the course of answering research questions 4 and 5.

3.6 Content Categories

Wimmer and Dominick asserted that at the heart of any content is the category system used to classify media content. The precise makeup of this system varies with the subject under

study. Barelson (1952 p.147) is of the view that “Particular studies have been productive to the extent that the categories were clearly formulated and well adapted to the problem and content.”

However, the units of analysis mentioned were coded and measured using some defined content categories through employing Priori Coding in an attempt to achieve a mutually, exclusive, exhaustive and reliable category system. The following were deduced from the units of analysis and defined accordingly. However, a **coding sheet** was used as an instrument for data collection. Hence, the data gathered was presented and analysed using descriptive method of data analysis.

3.7 Definition of Content Categories

This study is made up of two broad categories:

1. SDG Goals I-IV (poverty, hunger, health and Quality Education)
2. Other SDGs or other developmental news.

The above news categories were described based on the previous studies on development journalism including Kelleher (2014), Yusha’u (2014), Alkali (2011) and Onyeizu(2011).

1) **SDG Goal 1. (No poverty):** This means to end poverty in all forms everywhere. This includes the news stories, editorials, feature articles/opinions and news analysis that geared towards the end of unemployment and all other forms. It further categorized into following classifications:

- I. Government Ministerial Bodies, and Agencies (GMB& A) that aim at poverty eradication either in form of government’s speeches or policies such as Social Investment Programme (which focuses on providing Social Safety Nets for the poor, welfare for the unemployed and job creation and skill enhancement); Conditioned Cash Transfer (CCT); Home- Grown School Feeding Programme

(HGSFP); Government Enterprises and Empowerment Programme (GEEP) and N-Power.

- II. Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs): These are news stories that involve the activities of CSOs and NGOs in promoting SDG goals I that is fighting against poverty.
 - III. International Development Partners (IDP): this relates to International bodies and development agencies like the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) and other International agencies either in form of government or non-governmental bodies. News stories that cover the activities of the said bodies on SDG goal I fall under this category.
 - IV. Private Donors: stories related to the funding of SDG goal I both by the local and international bodies.
 - V. Other actors related to SDG goal I (OSDG[I]): these are the news stories from other sources that are outside the above-mentioned actors but are related to SDG goal I.
- 2) **SDGs Goal 2 (Zero hunger):** End hunger, achieve food security and improved nutrition and promote sustainable agriculture. The defined news stories, news analysis, editorials or feature articles that tackle any programme both from government ministries, agencies, parastatals or Non- government organizations (NGOs) or Community Based Organizations (CBOs) as detailed below:

I. Government Ministerial Bodies, and Agencies (GMB& A). The news stories, editorials, feature articles/opinions and news analysis that consider any programme, policy drivers and implementation that fight against hunger either by the government functionaries, government agencies, government speeches, programmes that intend to end hunger as well as all the related issues on agricultural support and improvements. The government programmes that are intended to fight against hunger to be considered in the data collection include the following:

- The Green Alternative Agriculture Promotion Policy.
- Staple Crops Processing Zones (SCPZ).
- Nigeria Incentive-Based Risk- Sharing System for Agricultural Lending (NIRSAL).
- Rural Finance Institution Building Programme (RUFIN).
- Anchor Borrowers' Programme (ABP).
- Commercial Agricultural Credit Scheme (CACS)
- Youth Enterprise with Innovation in Nigeria (Youwin).

II. Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs): These are new stories, feature articles and editorials that involves the activities of CSOs and NGOs in promoting SDG goals II that is ensuring zero hunger is prevailed among the inhabitants of Nigeria.

III. International Development Partners (IDP): this relates to international bodies like International Funds for Agricultural Development (IFAD), the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the United Nations Development

Programme (UNDP), the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) and the rest. News stories that feature the activities of the said bodies on SDG goal II falls under this category.

- IV. Private Donors: stories related to the funding of SDG goal II both by local and international bodies.
 - V. Other SDG goal II (OSDG [II]): these are news stories from other actors that are outside the above-mentioned items but are related to SDG goal II.
- 3) **SDGs Goal 3 (Health and well being):** Ensure healthy lives and promotes well being for all at all stages. This involves the selected units of analysis that geared towards health improvements that aim at reducing maternal death, Neonatal mortality, the spread of contagious and communal diseases like HIV infection, Tuberculosis, Hepatitis B infections; Malaria; programmes that require interventions against tropical diseases, mortality of cardiovascular diseases such as cancer, diabetes or chronic respiratory diseases and the rest; provision of health facilities; construction of health sectors and any other programme or projects that will lead to human development and capacity through any of the following bodies as sub- categorized below:
- I. Government and Ministerial bodies and agencies (GMB&A): These involve coverage on the units of analysis that include government speeches, programmes and policies from the government ministerial agencies, departments and parastatals or related bodies that geared towards health improvement and general welfare of the society as earlier indicated. It also includes government programmes like National Health Insurance Scheme (NHIS) and

- II. Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and Non-Government Organizations(NGOs): programmes and activities of CSOs and NGOs, CBOs different bodies of health Union from medicines, pharmacists and the rest as well as scientific research and findings and investigations on health-related matter that aim at the provision, and improvement of health, and general wellbeing of the Nigerian inhabitants.
 - III. International Development Partners (IDP): this relates to International bodies like the United Nations Children, and Education Fund (UNICEF), the World Health Organization (WHO), the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID), and other related international health bodies alike. News stories that feature the activities of the said bodies on SDG goal III falls under this category.
 - IV. Private Donors: stories related to the funding of SDG goal III by both local and international bodies.
 - V. Other sources related to SDG goal III (OSDG [III]): these are news stories from other sources or actors that are outside the above-mentioned actors related to SDG goal III.
- 4) **SDG Goal IV (Quality Education):** Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all. This includes establishing vocational and technical institutes, *Almajiri* and nomadic education-based schools. Enhanced Digital skills for health among other related issues. The followings sub-categories concerned with the analysis of data are:

- I. Government and Ministerial bodies and agencies (GMB&A): These involve coverage on the units of analysis that include government

speeches, programmes and policies from the government ministerial agencies, departments and parastatals that geared towards the provision of quality education.

- II. Civil Society Organizations (CSOs) and Non-Government Organizations (NGOs): programmes and activities of CSOs and NGOs, and CBOs that aim at the provision of inclusive equitable and quality education for all.
- III. International Development Partners (IDP): This relates to International bodies like the World Bank, the International Monetary Fund (IMF), the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) and so on. News stories that feature the activities of the said bodies and other related bodies on SDG goal IV fall under this category.
- IV. Private Donors: stories related to the funding of SDG goal IV by both the local and international bodies.
- V. Other SDG goal IV (OSDG [IV]): these are news stories from other sources or actors not mentioned above related to SDG goal IV.

2. Other SDGs: These are the categories of news stories that are related to other SDG goals, indicators or targets (apart from Goals I-IV) which are considered in the Sustainable Development agenda and regarded as the elements for attaining sustainable development. These categories were **named as Other SDGs** in the coding sheets and have the following definitions:

SDGs V (Gender Equality): the following category falls under SDGs IV

1. (Women and Children): These are news stories related to Women, gender equality and child welfare: women's cooperatives, domestic violence, sexual violence, abuse and harassment. All other forms of inequality that was contained in **SDGs 10 (Reduced Inequality)** fall under this category

SDGs VI: (Clean Water and Sanitation): this categorised into following:

2. Infrastructure: it relates to stories on the provision of water and sanitation, rehabilitation, construction of roads, rails, provision of social amenities, tourism, cultural institutions fall on this category.

SDGs VII (affordable and Clean Energy): it contains the categories below:

3. Power and Energy: stories on power and Energy, news on electricity and power generation services fall under this category.

SDGs VIII (Decent work and Economic Growth): and SDGs XII (Responsible Consumption and production):

4. Finance and Business/Economic news: stories related to the activities and programmes on Nigerian financial and business activities, programmes on financial and business activities, private sector business development, banking sector, tax and revenue generation, general economic activities, budget and budgetary activities, trade investments, and consumerism.
5. Labour, Jobs and Career: news related to workers' rights, workers' promotion of appointment, training and welfare associated with workers and pensioners, workers health, occupational safety, industrial strikes, and any other related news. Stories on careers and appointments from private sectors those outside of governing bodies fall into this category.
6. Youth: news on youth development, news related to National Youth Service Corps (NYSC).

SDGs VIII (Industry, Innovation and Infrastructure): the following categories fall under SDGs 9.

7. Industrialization: These are industrial development stories, factories construction.
8. Science and Technology: These are knowledge-Based development news, science and technology findings and research; it also concerned stories on scientific and technological development in Nigeria.

SDGs XI (Sustainable Cities and Communities and Communication): this constitutes the following categories.

9. Housing and Transportation: any news stories that are geared towards the provision of housing and transportation to the Nigerian people, this includes, problems of homeless, inadequate facilities in urban, house constructions, rural and urban migration, demolition and relocation of homes transportation of all kinds including air, maritime, sea, ocean, shipping and so on. Stories related to agencies like Federal Road Safety Services (FRSC) falls under this category.
10. Telecommunication/Media: Stories that are connected to telecommunication sectors includes Information Technology Based stories, network service providers, as news related to the media sector and its development.

SDGs XIII (Climate Action): the following categories are as follows:

11. Disaster and safety: disasters related to environment earthquakes, flooding, pollution, erosion, fire, car accidents, plane crash as well as safety measures taken by the governing bodies like Emergency Management agencies, public or community members

SDGs XIV (Conservative and Sustainable use of the Oceans, Seas and Marine Resources for Sustainable Development): this include below.

12. Oil, Gas and Mineral Resources: it means oil, Gas, mining and mineral resources stories related to NNPC, refineries, oil companies.

SDGs XV (Protect, restore, and promote terrestrial ecosystem and halt biodiversity loss):

13. Environment: stories in form of environmental activities include stories on climate change, and other related environmental protection policies and programmes aimed at the protection of the environment.

SDGs XVI (Promotion of Peaceful and Inclusive Societies for Sustainable Development):

14. Law and Judiciary: stories related to law, prosecution of the court of laws, judicial actions fall under this category.

15. Government and Governance: It refers to news on government activities, government functionaries speeches as well as and appointment from government functionaries from all three tiers of government.

16. Legislature: news on the activities of both upper and lower chambers legislative actions like the presentation of motions, bills at both the states and federal levels.

17. Politics: any related political activities and political crises, political speeches, endless political debates and general political rhetoric either from political parties and other political affiliate groups.

18. Security: it involves the activities of security agencies; Army, Police, DSS, Nigerian Immigration Services, Custom Services, Prisons and the rest that geared towards fighting against insecurity in Nigeria, speeches and activities made by the security personnel. Stories that geared towards promoting security were considered in this category

19. Corruption: news related to EFCC, IPCP and other body from all over the country that concerns any person in the country. News on looted funds, frauds and so on.

SDGs XVII (Partnership) This comprise the following categories:

20. Humanitarian: news stories related to to support and aids by all angles both national and international to internally displaced persons, (IDPs), or any assistance offered by any of the means. Also, donation of foodstuff to the orphans, widow and any form of humanitarian assistance fall under this category.
21. Crisis, Conflicts, Crime: these are news items from any sort of crime and conflicts like Boko Haram insurgency attacks, - Herders crises, middle belt and Niger Delta conflict and all forms of banditry, criminality as well as communal clashes.

3.8 Coding and Measurement of Content Categories

The study coded and measured the above-mentioned categories using at least three parameters:

1. **Direction of the Story:** under this, the study looked at if the story is positive, negative or neutral to the government's commitments towards the execution and implementation of SDG in Nigeria.
 - **Positive:** This means if the stories are supporting or encouraging the government policies towards SDGs Goals (I-IV).
 - **Negative:** means the news stories that are not supportive or discouraging to government policies, programmes and projects in respect to SDG goals (I-IV)
 - **Neutral:** The stories that are neutral and non biased in other words are neither supportive nor opposing to government policies, projects and programmes towards SDG goals (I-IV).

2. **Story Positioning /prominence:** under this, the researcher determined those SDGs goals (I-IV) stories that were placed in the lead front page, other front pages, inside, centre- spread and back pages.
 - **Lead front page:** the most important story of the day in newspaper such story is usually published on the front page of newspapers with the boldest or biggest headline. It dominates all other stories on the front page of the newspaper.
 - **Other front pages:** any other stories on the front page of the newspaper apart from the lead story.
 - **Inside page:** Any stories found inside newspaper different from the centre spread, front page and back page.
 - **Centre spread:** stories found in the centre or middle of the newspaper.
 - **Back page:** any stories found on the back page of the newspaper.
3. **The story Actors:** under this, the researcher determined the story players or actors using five strata either from government officials, NGOs/ CSOs/CBOs, International Development partners, Private donors or other sources apart from those mentioned earlier.
4. **The frequency of occurrence.** The research quantified the level of frequency of Occurrence of the analysed units of analysis that is news stories, news analysis, Editorials, features, and opinions on the SDGs I-IV

3.9 Inter-Coder Reliability

Research reliability is crucial to content analytical studies. It gives a content analysis work a form of objectivity if its measures and procedures are objectives. (Wimmer & Dominick,

2011). Krippendorff (2004) is of the view that, the degree to which a process can be replicated by different analysts, working under varying conditions, at different locations, or using different but functionally equivalent instruments. To be clear, the agreement is what we measure; reliability is what we wish to infer from it. In content analysis, reproducibility is arguably the most important interpretation of reliability. (p. 215). Furthermore, Potter and Levine-Donnestein (1999) note that re-productivity (reliability) requires a test-test process whereby different coders or raters analyze the same text, coding the set of content once each. If the judgments' of the coders are the same by producing the same coding pattern, the data generated can be regarded as reliable. This, therefore, implies that results generated from such data can be regarded as valid. Given that the "reliability problems usually grow out of the ambiguity of word meanings, category definitions, or other coding rules" (R.P. Weber, 1990, p. 15). According to Wimmer and Dominick (2011) " A study is reliable when repeated measurement of the same material results in similar decision or conclusions. Inter-coder reliability refers to the level of agreement among independent coders who code the same content using the same coding instrument. If the results fail to achieve reliability, something is amiss with the coders, the coding instructions, the category definitions, the units of analysis or some combination of these." (P.170).

For this study, two coders were employed and coded the manifest contents of the sampled editions of the two newspapers under study for one quarter (January to March), one serving as a master coder and a trained coder, to ensure inter-coder reliability in the coding process, Holsi's formula was adopted to determine the percentage of agreement between the coders.

$$\text{Reliability} = \frac{2(M)}{N_1 + N_2}$$

Where:

M = refers to the number of coding decision on which two coders agree and

N1 = Total number of coding decisions by the first coder

N2 = Total number of coding decisions by the second coder.

Therefore, Inter Coder Reliability = $\frac{2(M)}{N_1 + N_2}$

Where M = 710

N1=715

N2= 716

Thus, reliability = $\frac{2(710)}{715 + 716} = 0.99$ approximately to 1

Wimmer and Dominick (2011, p.175) advise that as a rule of thumb, most published content analyses typically report a minimum of (1), it means that the Hostli's formula sincerest shows a coefficient of (1), it means the inter-coder reliability between the two coders is (very high) As it cannot be more than (1) it invariably means that the reliability is perfect.

3.10 Method of Data Presentation and Analysis

The research employed a quantitative method of data collection and presentation. Hence, a descriptive form of data analysis was employed, where simple distribution tables, numbers percentage and scores were employed for ease of data analysis and interpretation and also aid in answering the research question.

3.11 Newspapers Profile under Study

3.11.1. *The Guardian* Newspaper

The Guardian newspaper was founded and published by the late Dr Alex Umerulbru (1945-2011). According to Nnabuiife (2006) cited in Nnadozie (2013) the first publication of the *Guardian* Newspaper came out on July 4, 1982, and it commenced publishing issues on visual arts from the first edition. From the onset, the styles of publication were reviews and art criticism. It is worthy to note that the newspaper was founded by a team of intellectuals,

mostly literacy scholars (authors, creative writers, critics and academics in humanities). There were such names as Wole Soyinka, Chinweizu, late Dr Stanley Macebu and Dr. Ogunbiyi and Dr Reuben Abati, who was a one time chairman of the editorial board.

The Guardian is an independent newspaper established to present balanced coverage of events and promote the best interest of Nigeria. It owns allegiance to no political party, ethnic community, religious sovereign of the federation of Nigeria in particular and Africa at large (Nnadozie, 2013). The *Guardian* paper Moreover, is a liberal newspaper committed to the best traditions and ideals of republican democracy. The newspaper believes that it's the responsibility of the government not only to protect and depend on the citizens but also to create the political, social, economic and cultural conditions in which all citizens may achieve their highest potential as human beings. It is committed to the principle of individual freedom, also believes that all citizens have obligations to serve the nation and rights to be discharged. (Nnadozie, 2013)

The Guardian newspaper does not in principle object to the ideology of free enterprises since it could be inconsistent with its commitment to individual liberty and freedom. It also believes that the state must judiciously intervene in the economic life of the nation to minimise the adverse effects of free and capital for their benefit.

As contained in *The Guardian* Year Dairy, 2007 cited in Nnadozie, (2013) the newspaper believes it is the duty of the state to ensure that less privileged citizens have reasonable and fair access to the necessities of life. The *Guardian* has subjected itself to upholding the virtues of justice, probity in public life, equal access to the nation's resources and held that fulfilling international obligations only if the paper's integrity are guaranteed and ensured. This, as enunciated by Nnadozie (2013) is the cause of gaining a good reputation as one of the most readable and circulated newspapers in Nigeria.

3.11.2 Daily Trust Newspaper

The *Daily Trust* Newspaper, a well-focused and market-driven was privately owned and published by the Media Trust Nigeria Limited, a sister publication of *Weekly Trust* have made its debut in January 2001. Being the first daily newspaper from the Federal Capital Territory, Abuja. The paper devotes about six pages to news coverage despite the special pages for crime stories, arts and entertainment. Information multilateral diplomacy, the newspaper devotes about four pages to international events. The paper offers feedback coming with its readership in form of letters to the editor using rib-cracking cartoons that share the ones. One of the features that is appreciated to the distinction of it from other newspapers is the use of consistent headline (that is what is exactly contained in the story headline) as against sensational headline that characterised in the use of colours in the splashing photographs. The use of lines to both specs appears so to be a distinct style.

The newspaper upholds the liberation principle and yet, the publication display profound regard for social responsibility in news coverage and editorial columns. Four of the powerful writers in the country have been brought into the Editorial Board as columnists. They are Mahmud Jega, Sam Nda Isaiah and Ujudud Sharif. Moreover, the *Weekly* and *Daily Trust* are now the largest circulating newspapers in Northern Nigeria the only newspaper whose print runs is in five digits, they are in addition the pioneers in colour production in the north. The *Daily Trust* building on the goodwill of the *Weekly* started production on five digits from inception.

The sales copies are distributed in towns and cities in the North, Lagos, Akure, Abeokuta and Ibadan in the South- West, Port Harcourt, Yenegoa, Benin, Calabar in the South-South, Onitsha, Owerri and Enugu in the South- East, and in several outlets in London, England.

It means that the reliability is perfect.

CHAPTER FOUR: DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

4.1 Results from the Analysis of *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* Newspapers

This chapter presents data analysis and interpretation of research findings. The two papers under study; *The Guardian* and *Daily Trust* were analysed according to the criteria indicated earlier in the research methodology (page 39). The chapter presents data and interprets the findings of the research in a descriptive form thus, answering the research questions. It begins with the data presentation, followed the interpretation of the data, and discussion on the research findings. Finally, the research questions were treated using a combined table of *Daily Trust* and the *Guardian* newspapers content analysed.

The study analysed the coverage of the two newspapers under study for twelve months as described in table 3.1 totaling the sum of 520 editions. The total number of copies was 522. However, two copies from *The Guardian* newspaper were not obtained for the dates of 05/07/2016 and 26//12/2016. This reduced the total copies of the two newspapers to 520 issues/copies. Analysis was conducted using five parameters that include; frequency of News stories in the coverage for SDGs I-IV and other SDGs (other development issues); story positioning of SDGs I-IV and other SDGs; direction of coverage of SDGs I-IV; story Actors/Major Players of SDGs I-IV as well as the journalistic genres (types) used in the coverage of SDGs I-IV.

Table 4.1 Frequency of News Coverage on SDGs I-IV by the *Daily Trust* Newspaper

Distribution of SDGs I-IV by the <i>Daily Trust</i>							
	Categories	Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Total	Percentage
	Poverty	82	74	111	122	389	13.96%

SDGs I-IV	Hunger	123	165	147	145	580	20.82%
	Health	266	183	192	230	871	31.26%
	Education	244	205	233	264	946	33.96%
	Total	715	627	683	761	2786	15.23%
Quarterly Distribution of other SDGs and Non-SDGs Coverage by the <i>Daily Trust</i>							
Other SDGs	Categories	Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Total	Percentage
	Business/Finances	590	486	613	611	2300	14.83%
	Housing/Transport	182	178	165	226	751	4.84%
	Environment/Climate	99	56	95	87	337	2.17%
	Infrastructure	84	90	80	75	329	2.12%
	Industrialization	45	31	31	33	140	0.90%
	Oil, Gas and Mineral Resources	148	137	116	82	483	3.11%
	Science/Technology	15	7	14	14	50	0.32%
	Power and Energy	100	117	120	132	469	3.02%
	Telecommunications/Media	193	123	109	149	574	3.70%
	Security	159	229	275	243	906	5.84%
	Disasters	128	116	83	85	412	2.66%
	Law and Judiciary	194	150	113	163	620	4.00%
	Humanitarian	57	66	41	30	194	1.25%
	Labour, Jobs & Careers	150	279	259	224	912	5.88%
	Corruption	166	207	150	148	671	4.33%
	Government/Governance	238	189	222	161	810	5.22%
	Legislature	141	172	81	133	527	3.40%
	Politics	658	611	617	574	2460	15.86%
	Crimes, Crises & Conflicts	562	566	491	467	2086	13.45%
Women and Children	53	96	61	69	279	1.80%	
Youth	51	51	48	52	202	1.30%	
Total	4013	3957	3784	3758	15512	84.77%	
Grand Total	4728	4584	4467	4519	18298	100.00%	

According to table 4.1 *Daily Trust* has total coverage of 2,786 news stories on SDGs I-IV out of which poverty recorded 389 issues representing 13.96 per cent. Hunger has a total of 580 issues represents by 20.82 per cent being the highest coverage on the four items content analysed. Education has 946 issues representing 33.96 closely followed by Health with 31.96 per cent of 869 issues. The analysis shows that *Daily Trust* covered most on Education and health-related matters; meanwhile little attention was given to poverty and hunger.

A cursory look at the same table on the coverage of other SDGs indicates that 21 items that constitute other development issues or other SDGs recorded the highest percentage of 84.77 per cent of 15,512 with Business/Finance and investment related issues having a largest coverage of 2300 issues represents by 18.43 percent closely followed by politics and crimes, crisis and conflicts with 2460 and 2086 issues equivalent to 15.86 and 13.45 percent respectively. The least on the record is scientific and technological coverage having a total coverage of 50 issues of 0.32 percent. In a nutshell, it can be summarized that *Daily Trust* did not give much emphasis on SDGs I-IV coverage in comparison to other SDGs with a total statistical figure of 15,512 issues against 2,786 issues recorded/covered for SDGs I-IV.

Table 4.2 Frequency of News Coverage on SDGs I-IV by the *Guardian* Newspaper

Distribution of SDGs I-IV by the <i>Guardian</i> Newspaper							
SDGs I-IV	Categories	Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Total	Percentage
	Poverty	69	48	63	65	245	9.59%
	Hunger	32	53	81	42	208	8.14%
	Health	276	250	350	305	1181	46.22%
	Education	185	208	304	224	921	36.05%
	Total	562(22.00%)	559(21.88%)	798(31.23%)	636(24.89%)	2555	14.03%
Quarterly Distribution of Other SDGs Coverage by The <i>Guardian</i> Newspaper							
Other SDGs	Categories	Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Total	Percentage
	Business/Finances	701	821	995	852	3369	21.52%
	Housing/Transport	288	272	363	359	1282	8.19%
	Environment/Climate	101	111	115	100	427	2.73%
	Infrastructure	52	55	151	109	367	2.34%
	Industrialization	72	58	67	77	274	1.75%
	Oil, Gas and Mineral Resources	190	211	141	174	716	4.57%
	Science/Technology	53	81	26	41	201	1.28%
	Power and Energy	129	127	178	145	579	3.70%
	Telecommunications/Media	295	299	429	363	1386	8.85%
	Security	161	175	215	142	693	4.43%
	Disasters	58	47	63	56	224	1.43%
	Law and Judiciary	251	266	146	239	902	5.76%
	Humanitarian	26	29	27	29	111	0.71%
Labour, Jobs	226	311	277	260	1074	6.86%	

&Careers							
Corruption	142	106	88	102	438	2.80%	
Government/Governance	155	89	142	118	504	3.22%	
Legislature	135	94	81	115	425	2.72%	
Politics	236	225	378	323	1162	7.42%	
Women and Children	31	27	32	28	118	0.75%	
Youth	18	49	13	9	89	0.57%	
Crimes, Crises & Conflicts	263	326	405	318	1312	8.38%	
Total	3583	3779	4332	3959	15653	85.97%	
Grand Total	4145(22.76%)	4338(23.82%)	5130(28.17%)	4595(25.24%)	18208	100.00%	

According to table 4.2 The *Guardian* covers 2555 issues of SDGs I-V out of which poverty has 245 issues representing 9.59 per cent, hunger records 208 issues averaging to 8.14 percent which is the least, health has the highest record of the total coverage with 1181 issues which represents 46.22 percent closely followed by education with 921 issues of 35.05 per cent. More so, the record shows a total coverage of 15653 of other SDGs from The *Guardian* this further revealed that 21 items that constitute other SDGs receive a largest proportion of 85.97 per cent. As it was obtained from the *Daily Trust*, Business, financial and investment related news stories receive a highest proportion of 22.52 percent of 3,369 issues widely followed by telecommunication and media related news stories with 1,386 issues corresponding to 8.85 percent, the least from the other SDGs coverage is news stories on youth related matters that receives 0.59 percent of 89 issues. The analysis further translates that while SDGs I-IV has a total frequency of news coverage of 2,555 issues other SDGs recorded a total coverage of 15,653 which further interpreted that like the *Daily Trust*, the *Guardian* also did not give adequate attention to the coverage of SDGs I-IV in terms of frequency of news occurrence.

A combined table for the two sampled newspapers was presented below. Although the focus of the research is on SDGs I-IV but, it is equally imperative to make a comparative analysis on

the two content categories to give a clear picture of the angle to which the press in Nigeria concentrates in terms of frequency of news coverage.

Table 4.3: Coverage of News Stories of SDGs I-IV and Other SDGs by The *Guardian* and *Daily Trust* Newspapers

Categories	Daily Trust Frequency	Percentage(%)	Guardian Frequency	Percentage (%)	Total frequency	Total Percentage (%)
Poverty	389	13.96%	245	9.59%	634	11.87%
Hunger	580	20.82%	208	8.14%	788	14.75%
Health	871	31.26%	1181	46.22%	2052	38.42%
Education	946	33.96%	921	36.05%	1867	34.96%
Total SDGs I-IV	2786	15.23%	2555	14.03%	5341	14.63%
Other SDGs	15512	84.77%	15653	85.97%	31165	85.37%
Grand Total	18298	100.00%	18208	100.00%	36506	100.00%

4.2: Frequency of Occurrence of SDGs I-IV in Comparison to Other SDGs (Other Development News) by the *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* Newspapers: Discussion of Findings

Data from table 4.3 reveals that the two newspapers analysed accounted for 5341 issues corresponding to 14.63% of SDGs I-IV while other SDGs consumed the highest coverage of 31165 with 85.37 per cent. This further indicates that in either case, the two newspapers under study give adequate attention to the coverage of SDGs I-IV during the year under study. The findings buttressed the work of Yushau (2011), Alkali (2011), Bello (2015) and also Chibueze (2015), Tshabangu (2013), Abana, (2017), Odozi&Nyam, (2014) that studied variance aspects of Education, Health and Agriculture and equally discovered minimum coverage of development issues. The findings of this study implied that newspapers in Nigeria deviate from the principles of Development Communication theory, as the study bedrock presupposes the important role the mass media has in the process of development McQuail (2005). The purpose of development communication is for the media “to contribute to national development goals, inform citizens of relevant government policies, introduce national leaders, foster political stability and promote national integration and education”

Domotob & Hall (1983) cited in Gefechu (2017, p.17-18). This is relevant to the actualization of SDGs I-IV. Upon its adoption as a national policy (SDGs), several policies on poverty alleviation were introduced this includes: Conditional Cash Transfer (CCT), Home- Grown School Feeding Programme (NHGSA), and Government Enterprise Empowerment Programme (GEEP) among others. There is a greater need to publicize the above policies to make government accountable and committed to the implementation of SDGs I-IV in particular and the whole SDG goals in general through constant or frequent coverage of SDGs, as the findings revealed that poverty receives a minimal reportage meanwhile, the two newspapers did not devote a single page on the coverage of government policies on poverty alleviation related matters. It can be assumed that the two newspapers did not adequately cover development issues as the research findings displayed. However, the newspapers are expected to cover more than what was obtained from the available statistical data as shown in the study, they are expected to act as reinforces and magnifiers of development while serving as causal agents in the process of national development. Schramm (1964), Seavaes (2008), Rogers (1976), Mabogunje (1991) among others.

Table 4.4: Story Positioning of SDGs I-IV and Other SDGs by the *Daily Trust* Newspaper

Prominence Given to SDGs I-IV by the Daily Trust							
Story Positioning	Poverty	Hunger	Health	Education	Total		
Lead Front page	7	8	3	12	30(1.08%)		
Front page others	2	0	1	5	8(0.29%)		
Inside page	379	568	864	926	2737(98.24%)		
Centre Spread	1	4	3	3	11(0.39%)		
Back page	0	0	0	0	0(0.00%)		
Total	389(13.96%)	580(20.82%)	871(31.26%)	946(33.96%)	2786(15.23%)		
Prominence Given to Other SDGs News Coverage by the <i>Daily Trust</i> Newspaper							
Categories	Lead front page	Other Front pages	Inside page	Centre spread	Back page	Total	Percentage

Business/Finances	70	23	2207	0	0	2300	14.83%
Housing/Transport	3	1	747	0	0	751	4.84%
Environment /Climate	1	0	336	0	0	337	2.17%
Infrastructure	1	1	327	0	0	329	2.12%
Industrialization	1	0	139	0	0	140	0.90%
Oil, Gas and Mineral Resources	19	5	459	0	0	483	3.11%
Science /Technology	0	0	50	0	0	50	0.32%
Power and Energy	8	5	456	0	0	469	3.02%
Telecommunications /Media	6	0	568	0	0	574	3.70%
Security	32	7	867	0	0	906	5.84%
Disasters	12	0	400	0	0	412	2.66%
Law and Judiciary	12	1	607	0	0	620	4.00%
Humanitarian	0	0	194	0	0	194	1.25%
Labour, Jobs &Careers	12	10	890	0	0	912	5.88%
Corruption	58	29	584	0	0	671	4.33%
Government/Governance	47	14	749	0	0	810	5.22%
Legislature	19	0	508	0	0	527	3.40%
Politics	27	0	2433	0	0	2460	15.86%
Women and Children	0	0	279	0	0	279	13.45%
Youth	0	0	202	0	0	202	1.80%
Crimes, Crises & Conflicts	16	0	2070	0	0	2086	1.30%
Total	344(2.22%)	96(0.62%)	15072(97.16%)	0(0.00%)	0(0.00%)	15512	84.77%
Grand Total	374(2.04%)	104(0.57%)	17809(97.33%)	11(0.06%)	0(0.00%)	18298	100.00%

The database in table 4.4 above shows that most of the SDGs I-IV coverage was placed inside the pages of *Daily Trust* having total issues of 2737 representing 98.24 per cent out of the total coverage of 2786. Lead story front, centre spread and other front pages recorded minimal coverage of 30(1.08%), 11(0.39%) and 8(0.29%) issues respectively while back page did not receive a single record this is because *Daily Trust* paper devoted its back page for Columnists and short stories on sports. Similarly, the same table also indicates the largest coverage of other SDGs inside the newspaper pages with coverage of 15072 issues representing 97.16 per cent. The lead story front page has total coverage of 344 (2.22%) and other front pages have 96 (0.62%), the least from the total record was the coverage placed on

the center spread page with 11 issues corresponding to 0.06 percent of the total coverage while back page has no single record as displayed from the findings.

Table 4.5: Story Positioning of SDGs I-IV and Other SDGs by the *Guardian* Prominence

Prominence Given to SDGs I-IV by the <i>Guardian</i> Newspaper							
Story Positioning	Poverty	Hunger	Health	Education	Total		
Lead Front page	6	3	7	3	19(0.74%)		
Front page others	3	3	24	7	37(1.45%)		
Inside page	236	202	1150	911	2499(97.81%)		
Centre Spread	0	0	0	0	0(0.00%)		
Back page	0	0	0	0	0(0.00%)		
Total	245(9.59%)	208(8.14%)	1181(46.22%)	921(36.05%)	2555(14.03%)		
Prominence Given to Other SDGs News Coverage by the <i>Guardian</i> Newspaper							
Categories	Lead front page	Other Front pages	Inside page	Centre spread	Back page	Total	Percentage
Business/Finances	67	64	3238	0	0	3369	21.51%
Housing/Transport	11	11	1260	0	0	1282	8.19%
Environment /Climate	6	12	409	0	0	427	2.73%
Infrastructure	0	5	362	0	0	367	2.34%
Industrialization	1	2	271	0	0	274	1.75%
Oil, Gas and Mineral Resources	26	35	655	0	0	716	4.57%
Science /Technology	0	0	201	0	0	201	1.28%
Power and Energy	5	10	564	0	0	579	3.70%
Telecommunications /Media	6	20	1360	0	0	1386	8.85%
Security	8	32	653	0	0	693	4.42%
Disasters	2	6	216	0	0	224	1.43%
Law and Judiciary	17	27	858	0	0	902	5.76%
Humanitarian	0	1	110	0	0	111	0.71%
Labour, Jobs &Careers	6	5	1063	0	0	1074	6.86%
Corruption	24	40	374	0	0	438	2.80%
Government/Governance	13	26	465	0	0	504	3.22%
Legislature	16	25	384	0	0	425	2.71%
Politics	19	43	1100	0	0	1162	7.42%
Women and Children	0	1	117	0	0	118	0.75%
Youth	0	1	88	0	0	89	0.57%
Crimes, Crises & Conflicts	20	41	1251	0	0	1312	8.38%
Total	247(1.58)	407(2.60%)	14999(95.82)	0(0.00)	0(0.00%)	1565	85.97%

	%))	%)	%))	3	
Grand Total	266(1.46%)	444(2.44%)	17498(96.10%)	0(0.00%)	0(0.00%)	18208	100.00%

From table 4.5 above it can be observed that, most of the news stories published by the *Guardian* for the year under study was placed inside the newspaper pages with 2499 issues this was represented by 97.81 per cent out of the total coverage of 2555, while 19 and 37 issues position in the lead front page and other front pages respectively, the back page did not receive a single record from the total coverage. Based on the above data, it can be summarized that the *Daily Trust* SDGs I-IV did not received maximum prominence in terms of story positioning or placement by the *Guardian* newspaper.

Statistical data on the same table above exhibits prominence attached to other SDGs this translates that, from the total coverage of 15,653 issues published by the sampled newspaper (*Guardian*) for the year under study 14,999 issues appeared inside the newspaper pages represented by 95.82 per cent, lead front page and other front pages which are the most important pages of any newspaper recorded 247 of 1.58 per cent and 407 of 2.60 per cent respectively. The analysis and interpretation from table 4.4 displayed inadequate prominence in the coverage of SDGs I-IV by way of story placement, in other words, they have not been adequately covered in a way of giving prominence by the *Guardian* newspaper for the year under study.

Table 4.6: Story Positioning of SDGs I-IV Coverage by *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* Newspapers

Daily Trust Coverage							
Story Positioning	Poverty	Hunger	Health	Education	Total		
Lead Front page	7	8	3	12	30(1.08%)		
Front page others	2	0	1	5	8(0.29%)		
Inside page	379	568	864	926	2737(98.24%)		
Centre Spread	1	4	3	3	11(0.39%)		
Back page	0	0	0	0	0(0.00%)		
Total	389	580	871	946	2786(52.16%)		
The <i>Guardian</i> Newspaper Coverage							
Lead Front page	6	3	7	3	19(0.74%)		
Other front page	3	3	24	7	37(1.45%)		
Inside page	236	202	1150	911	2499(97.81%)		
Centre Spread	0	0	0	0	0(0.00%)		
Back page	0	0	0	0	0(0.00%)		
Total	245	208	1181	921	2555(47.84%)		
Grand total	634	788	2052	1867	5341(100.00%)		
Story Placement of other SDGs by the <i>Daily Trust</i> and <i>The Guardian</i> Newspapers							
Categories	Lead front page	Other Front page	Inside page	Centre spread	Back page	Total	Percentage
<i>Daily Trust</i> newspaper							
Other SDGs	344(2.22%)	96(0.62%)	15072(97.16%)	0(0.01%)	0(0.00%)	15512	49.77%
<i>Guardian</i> Newspaper							
Other SDGs	247(1.58%)	407(2.60%)	14999(95.82%)	0(0.00%)	0(0.00%)	15653	50.23%
Grand Total	591(1.90%)	503(1.61%)	30071(96.49%)	0(0.00%)	0(0.00%)	31165	100.00%

4.3: Story Positioning/Prominence of SDGs I-IV Coverage in comparison to other SDGs by the *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* Newspapers: Discussion of Findings

The importance of the development news category may be dependent not only on the number of stories published but on the way and manner in which newspapers positions such stories

(Kelleher, 2014). Findings from table 4.6 expound that most of SDGs I-IV were featured inside the pages of two sampled papers content analyses with the total coverage of 2737 issues (98.24%) from *Daily Trust* and 2499 (97.81%) from *The Guardian*, this further indicates that the total SDGs (I-IV) coverage of 5341 issues from the two newspapers 5236 issues accounted to 98.03 per cent appeared inside the newspaper pages while only 49 issues corresponding to 0.92 per cent were placed in the lead front page while 45 issues representing 0.84 per cent featured in the other front page. No single story was featured on the back pages of the two newspapers for a reason that *Daily Trust* devoted its back page for columnists and short stories on sports, *The Guardian* on the other hand dedicated its back page to articles.

Also, story placement of other SDGs as shown from the analytical data revealed a higher disparity in the positioning of stories in the lead front page and other front pages with 591 issues equivalent to 1.90 per cent and 503 averaging to 1.61 per cent respectively. The implication of the findings of this study has further signified how developmental issues were neglected and not given reasonable attention in the Nigerian newspaper pages especially when compared to other sensational news like the economy, crimes, politics and so on [tables 4.4 and 4.5] Tshabangu (2013) although, most of these issues have their designated pages, Nigerian newspapers still report these issues on specified pages/sections to show the level of prominence accorded to such issues, and these issues especially politics seem the most preferred because of the presence of conflict as Onyeizu and Binta (2014) citing Weber (1990 and Oso & Odunlami (2008) uphold this assertion on reportage of health-related matters enunciated that health beats is not particularly high news beat like politics or economics.

It is essential to state that if Nigeria newspapers can consistently and strategically give prominent attention to development issues specifically SDGs I-IV through their lead stories and placement on other important pages/sections it may go a long way in setting agenda on

development issues as Davis (2009) established an important relationship between media reports and people's ranking of public issues. The Agenda Setting Theory, which was one of the study theoretical frameworks, expressed an important correlation between the rate at which the media cover a story and the extent to which people think that story is imperative. That is to say, the media has a pivotal role to set agenda on development issues such as SDGs I-IV. It is further argued that editors act as gatekeepers of mass-mediated messages (Mc Comb and Shaw, 1977). They can provide sustained and prominent coverage of issues, while others are marginalised or ignored. The agenda-setting is one of the most imperative theories while analysing media contents because it exposes media pervasive role in development communication. However, using agenda-setting theory and its proper application is a classical example of how we can use the theory in setting agenda that would bring the SDGs I-IV into the public domain and make government committed to their basic responsibilities.

Table 4.7: Direction of Coverage of SDGs I-IV through Units of analysis by the *Daily Trust* Newspaper

Story type	Positive	Negative	Neutral	Total	Percentage
Editorials	34	15	3	52	1.67%
Features/Opinions	94	35	40	169	5.41%
New Analysis	43	66	7	116	3.71%
News Stories	2179	373	234	2786	89.21%
Total	2350(75.25%)	489(15.66%)	284(9.09%)	3123	100.00%
The Direction of Coverage through Content Categories by the <i>Daily Trust</i> Newspaper					
Categories	Positive	Negative	Neutral	Total	Percentage
Poverty	362	28	9	399	12.78%
Hunger	481	131	70	682	21.84%
Health	701	167	133	1001	32.05%
Education	806	163	72	1041	33.33%

Total	2350(75.25%)	489(15.66%)	284 (9.09%)	3123	100.00%
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Table 4.7 above indicates a general analysis and coverage of SDGs I-IV through the four content categories and the four units of analysis. A critical analysis of the table above indicates that coverage of SDGs I-IV is encouraging or rather positive from the records of all the four units of analysis as they received the highest record except for news analysis which records negative as the highest, the direction in the coverage of SDGs I-V having 66 issues out of 116 issues of the total record. In totality, news stories having 2350 issues representing 75.25 per cent was recorded as positive or supportive to government policies, programmes and projects, 489 of 15.66 per cent were distantly reported in a negative form or rather discouraging to government's policies, projects, and programmes while the least on the record is 284 issues representing 9.09 per cent recorded to be balanced or neutral in the coverage of SDGs I-IV.

In the same vein, the same table also considers the direction of coverage in terms of the four content categories and it was revealed that unlike what was obtained in the direction of coverage through the units of analysis, all the four contents categories which represent SDGs I-IV was recorded positive with the highest record of 2350 (75.25%) distantly followed by the negative and neutral coverage with the percentage of 15.66 and 9.09 respectively.

Table 4.8: Direction of Coverage of SDGs I-IV through Units of Analysis by *The Guardian* Newspaper

Categories	Positive	Negative	Neutral	Total	Percentage
Editorials	22	9	2	33	1.14%
Features/Opinions	104	85	32	221	7.65%
New Analysis	28	10	43	81	2.80%
News Stories	1739	353	463	2555	88.41%
Total	1893(65.50%)	457(15.81%)	540(18.69%)	2890	100.00%

SDGs I-IV Direction of Coverage through Content Categories by <i>The Guardian</i> Newspaper					
Categories	Positive	Negative	Neutral	Total	Percentage
Poverty	245	26	9	280	9.69%
Hunger	171	52	20	243	8.41%
Health	700	183	430	1313	45.43%
Education	771	202	81	1054	36.47%
Total	1887(65.29%)	463(16.02%)	540(18.69%)	2890	100.00%

Table 4.8 provides general coverage of SDGs I-IV direction of coverage. Meanwhile, for ease of understanding the analysis and interpretation of the above statistical data from the table above, the study analyses the content of the paper (*The Guardian*) in two formats. While the former provides analysis on the direction of reportage through the four analysed units of coverage the latter concentrates on analysing the content categories. However, from table 4.8 above, the study indicates that the four units analysed as having a total coverage of 2890 out of which 1893 stories were reported as positive representing 65.50 per cent, 457 issues of 18.41 per cent was reported in a negative form and the remaining 540 issues equivalent to 18.69 per cent was balanced in the course of reporting that is to say that, they are neither favorable nor discouraging to the government's projects, policies or programmes. Similarly, analysis from the content categories also exhibits that all the stories from the four content categories were reported positively having 1887 issues represented by 65.29 per cent, while 463 of 16.0per cent was reported in a negative form and 540 issues equivalent to 18.69 per cent was balanced or neutral in the course of reporting SDGs I-IV by *The Guardian* newspaper. However, based on the above findings it can be submitted that *The Guardian* does reports SDGs I-IV in support of the government's policies, projects and programmes in the process of implementation of SDGs I-IV.

Table 4.9: Direction of Coverage of SDGs I-IV by *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* Newspapers

Categories	Direction of coverage	Daily Trust Frequency	Percentage	Guardian Frequency	Percentage	Total Frequency	Total Percentage
Poverty	Positive	362	90.72%	245	87.50%	607	89.40%
	Negative	28	7.02%	26	9.29%	54	7.95%
	Neutral	9	2.26%	9	3.21%	18	2.65%
	Total	399	12.78%	280	9.69%	679	11.29%
Hunger	Positive	481	70.53%	171	70.37%	652	70.49%
	Negative	131	19.21%	52	21.40%	183	19.78%
	Neutral	70	10.26%	20	8.23%	90	9.73%
	Total	682	21.83%	243	8.41%	925	15.38%
Health	Positive	701	70.03%	700	53.31%	1401	60.54%
	Negative	167	16.68%	183	13.94%	350	15.13%
	Neutral	133	13.29%	430	32.75%	563	24.33%
	Total	1001	32.05%	1313	45.43%	2314	38.48%
Education	Positive	806	77.42%	771	73.14%	1577	75.27%
	Negative	163	15.66%	202	19.17%	365	17.42%
	Neutral	72	6.92%	81	7.69%	153	7.30%
	Total	1041	33.33%	1054	36.47%	2095	34.84%
	Grand total	3123	100.00%	2890	100.00%	6013	100.00%

4.4: The Direction of Coverage of SDGs I-IV by the *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* Newspapers: Discussion of Findings

From the analysis of table 4.9 it indicates that the two newspapers analysed are supportive to government policies, projects and programmes in the coverage of SDGs as the analysis above shows both four content categories recorded the highest proportion of positivity in the course of their coverage. Issues related to poverty record 607 representing 89.40 per cent, those related to hunger has 652 positive records with 70.49 per cent while health and education have 1401 and 1577 equivalent to 60.54 per cent and 75.27 per cent respectively. Negative records of the four categories show that poverty has the least record of 54 issues equivalent to 7.95 per cent, hunger receives 183 representing 19.78 per cent, health and education, on the other hand, have the highest negative records of 350 and 365 with a

proportion of 15.13 per cent and 17.42 per cent accordingly. More so, the reportage of SDGs I-IV was neither supportive nor opposing to government policies, programmes and projects in the process of actualization of SDGs I-IV.

Overall, it must be stated that the direction of coverage by the *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* newspapers on SDGs I-IV is widely encouraging to the implementation of SDGs in Nigeria. In other words, the content analysis of the two newspapers demonstrated some very positive signs to development communication approach. The media as the theory suggests must be supportive rather than critical of government policies in its efforts to provide socio-economic development to the governed, they must be favourable to good news as bad news are to be treated with caution because it can be economically damaging to Third World nations like Nigeria in its process for growth and change. Lent (1978, p.12) affirmed this in the statement below:

Because Third World nations are newly emergent, they need time to develop their institutions. During this initial period of growth, stability and unity must be sought. Criticism must be minimized and the public faith in government institutions and policies must be encouraged. Media must cooperate, according to this guided press concept, by stressing positive, development-inspired news, by ignoring negative societal or oppositions characteristics and by supporting government ideologies and plan.

Moreover, the findings of the study buttressed the assumptions made by Usman cited in Odozi and Nyam (2014) when expressing the role of the press in national development policies and public discourse with reference to agenda-setting function of the media. He stated that the news media can help raise public awareness of societal development problems and issues, create public consciousness about development, inform people and help them to make the right choices, influence policymakers to pay attention and reflect public opinion.

Table 4.10: Distribution of Key players/Sources of SDGs Goals (I-IV) News stories Coverage by the Daily Trust Newspaper

CATEGORIES	SOURCES/ PLAYERS	Jan-Mar	April-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Total
POVERTY	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	44	40	60	69	213(55.00%)
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	37	34	41	42	154(40.00%)
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	1	0	9	7	17(4.00%)
	Private Donors	0	0	0	0	0(0.00%)
	Other Related SDGs on Poverty	0	0	1	4	5(1.00%)
Total		82(21.08%)	74(19.02%)	111(28.53%)	122(31.36%)	389(14.00%)
HUNGER	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	45	51	49	54	199(34.00%)
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	74	89	70	71	304(52.00%)
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	0	16	14	8	38(70.00%)
	Private Donors	1	2	0	1	4(1.00%)
	Other Related SDGs on Hunger	3	7	14	11	35(6.00%)
Total		123(21.21%)	165(28.45%)	147(25.34%)	145(25.00%)	580(21.00%)
HEALTH	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	155	88	93	93	429(49.00%)
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	86	66	71	100	323(37.00%)
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	0	5	9	22	36(4.00%)
	Private Donors	8	1	4	1	14(2.00%)
	Other Related SDGs on Health	17	23	15	14	69(8.00%)
Total		266(30.54%)	183(21.01%)	192(22.04%)	230(26.41%)	871(31.00%)
EDUCATION	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	142	115	117	163	537(56.77%)
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	69	53	82	76	280(29.60%)
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	0	3	16	11	30(3.17%)
	Private Donors	5	6	1	5	17(1.78%)
	Other Related SDGs on Education	28	28	17	9	82(8.67%)
Total		244(25.79%)	205(21.67%)	233(24.63%)	264(27.91%)	946(34.00%)
GRAND TOTAL		715(25.66%)	627(22.51%)	683(24.52%)	761(27.31%)	2786(100.00%)
Summary of Sources/Major Players in the Coverage of SDGs I-IV by the Daily Trust						
Actors of news stories	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	213	199	429	537	1378(49.46%)
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	154	304	323	280	1061(38.08%)
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	17	38	36	30	121(4.34%)
	Private Donors	0	4	14	17	35(1.26%)
	Other Related SDGs I-IV	5	35	69	82	191(6.86%)
Total		389(13.96%)	580(20.82%)	871(31.26%)	946(33.96%)	2786(100.00%)

The analysis from table 4.10 provides general analysis on the actors/players who participated in the coverage of SDGs I-IV by The *Daily Trust* newspaper, for ease of interpretation and comprehension a summary table was presented in the same table and shows that *Daily Trust* actors or major players partake in the coverage of SDGs I-IV were mainly from the Government ministerial bodies and agencies with the highest figure of 1378 to 49.46 per cent, Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), Community Based Organizations (CBOs), was closely followed with 1061 issues representing 38.08 per cent, while private donors received a minimal record of 35 issues representing 1.26 per cent. International Development Partners as key players received 191 issues equivalent to 6.86 per cent and, other related actors not specified has 121 issues equivalent to 4.34 per cent. This analysis indicates that actors that partake in the coverage of SDGs I-IV were mostly from government ministerial bodies and agencies closely followed by Non-governmental organizations, Civil Society Organizations and Community Based Organizations, the least on the items content analyzed was Private donors and international development partners who are also part of the key players in the implementation of SDGs I-IV.

Table 4.11: Sources/Major players of SDGs Goals (I-IV) News Stories Coverage by The Guardian Newspaper

CATEGORIES	Sources/Players	Jan-Mar	April-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Total	Percentage
POVERTY	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	28	28	30	33	119	48.57%
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	34	14	25	27	100	40.82%
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	1	6	3	2	12	4.90%
	Private Donors	3	0	0	0	3	1.22%
	Other Related SDGs on Poverty	3	0	5	3	11	4.49%
Total		69	48	63	65	245	9.59%
HUNGER	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	21	32	37	29	119	57.21%
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	5	10	23	10	48	23.08%
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	2	9	8	3	22	10.58%
	Private Donors	1	0	1	0	2	0.96%
	Other Related SDGs on Hunger	3	2	12	0	17	8.17%
Total		32	53	81	42	208	8.14%
HEALTH	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	96	63	67	47	273	23.12%
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	124	140	222	205	691	58.51%
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	13	21	34	41	109	9.23%
	Private Donors	5	3	4	0	12	1.02%
	Other Related SDGs on Health	38	23	23	12	96	8.13%
Total		276	250	350	305	1181	46.22%
EDUCATION	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	93	78	124	109	404	43.87%
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	62	107	151	102	422	45.82%
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	11	11	7	6	35	3.80%
	Private Donors	3	5	5	4	17	1.85%
	Other Related SDGs on Education	16	7	17	3	43	4.67%
Total		185	208	304	224	921	36.05%
GRAND TOTAL		562	559	798	636	2555	100.00%

Summary of Sources Key Players Used in the Coverage of SDGs I-IV by The Guardian Newspapers

Actors of news stories	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	119	119	273	404	915(35.81%)
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	100	48	691	422	1261(49.35%)
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	12	22	109	35	178(6.97%)
	Private Donors	3	2	12	17	34(1.33%)
	Other Related SDGs on Poverty	11	17	96	43	167(6.54%)
Total		245(9.59%)	208(8.14%)	1181(46.22%)	921(36.05%)	2555(100.00%)

Table 4.11 and above provides a general data analysis on the major players in the coverage of SDGs I-IV by the *Guardian* newspaper, a summary data from the same (table 4.10) was provided to ease data interpretation however, data from the summary table implied that the major players/actors in the reportage of SDGs I-IV were Civil Society Organizations (CBOs, Non-government Organizations, (NGOs), Community Based Organizations (CBOs) with the highest record of 1261 equivalent to 49.35 per cent, the next major player is, government ministerial bodies and agencies having 915 issues representing 35.81 per cent the least record of the major actors are from private donors with 34 issues equivalent to 1.33 per cent, while International Development Partners and other related actors receive 178 and 168 issues with 6.97 and 6.54 per cent respectively. In a nutshell, it can be concluded that the major actors played in the coverage of SDGs I-IV by the *Guardian* newspaper were mostly from the Non-governmental Organizations, CBOs and other scientific research findings closely followed by Government's ministries, agencies and parastatals.

Table 4.12: Sources/Major Players used in the Coverage of SDGs I-IV by *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* Newspapers

Daily Trust Coverage						
CATEGORIES		Poverty	Hunger	Health	Education	Total
Sources/players						
Actors of news stories	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	213	199	429	537	1378(49.46%)
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	154	304	323	280	1061(38.08%)
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	17	38	36	30	121(4.34%)
	Private Donors	0	4	14	17	35(1.26%)
	Other Related SDGs on Poverty	5	35	69	82	191(6.86%)
Total		389(13.96%)	580(20.82%)	871(31.26%)	946(33.96%)	2786(100.00%)
Guardian Newspaper Coverage						
Actors of news stories	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	119	119	273	404	915
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	100	48	691	422	1261
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	12	22	109	35	178
	Private Donors	3	2	12	17	34
	Other Related SDGs on Poverty	11	17	96	43	167
	Total		245(9.59%)	208(8.14%)	1181(46.22%)	921(36.05%)
	Grant Total	634	788	2052	1867	5341
Summary Table Displaying Sources/Major Players of SDGs I-IV Coverage by <i>Daily Trust</i> and <i>The Guardian</i> Newspapers						
CATEGORIES		Poverty	Hunger	Health	Education	Total
Actors/Players						
Actors of news stories	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)	332	318	702	941	2293
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)	254	352	1014	702	2322
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)	29	60	145	65	299
	Private Donors	3	6	26	34	69
						42.93%
						43.48%
						5.60%
						1.29%

	Other Related SDGs on Poverty	16	52	165	125	358 6.70%
Total		634 11.87%	788 14.75%	2052 38.42%	1867 34.96%	5341 100.00%

4.5: Sources /Major Players of SDGs I-IV Coverage by *Daily Trust* and *The Guardian* Newspapers: Discussion of Findings

Findings from Table 4.12 shows that the major players/sources in the coverage of SDGs I-IV collectively gathered by the two newspapers are mainly from Civil Society Organizations, Non-Government Organization's Community Based Organization, Medical experts or Intellectuals and the like with the highest proportion of 43.48 per cent closely followed by Government Ministerial bodies, its agencies and parastatals with a moderate record of 42.93 per cent. Though, *Daily Trust* record Government Agencies, and parastatals as the highest [table 4.7 & 4.8], *The Guardian* record highest on Civil Society Organizations and other related groups defined under the category [Table 4.9 & 4.10]]. The least actors as the findings revealed are the private donors that have 69 issues representing 1.29 per cent, while International Development Partners and other Actors not specified from the category has a proportion of 5.60 and 6.70 per cent respectively.

SDGs actors served as major pillars of the development agenda implementation process. For successful implementation of SDGs there must be greater attention on inter linkages in three areas: 1) Across sectors like finance, agriculture, energy and the like; 2) across societal actors (local authorities, government agencies, private sectors and civil society) and 3) between or among the low, medium and high-income countries. (Jariyesimi, 2016, p.14). This further indicates the important aspect of actors like Civil Society Groups and government agencies in the implementation process of SDGs. Vigilant and socially engaged presses help to hold government and non-governmental agencies accountable to SDGs commitment and draw the

attention of those who have the responsibility of turning these lofty promises into reality. Meanwhile, Civil Society Groups has a pivotal role to play in SDGs planning and execution processes. This was contained in a blueprint that serves as a guide for stakeholders provided by the United Nations *Getting Started with Sustainable Development Goals: A guide to stakeholders* it posited that Civil Society has the capacity role to represent the needs of under-represented communities and regions this, however, make them critical partners in ensuring that SDGs strategies target the need of all segments of society and ensuring accountability for SDGs implementation second, they have an extensive experience in delivering services to the poor and can recommend appropriate intervention in different parts of the country. Therefore, they need to be represented in multi-stakeholders bodies, and thematic working groups for public consultations on important issues for SDGs planning.

There is also a strong correlation between the coverage of development issues such as SDGs and relevant stakeholders like government agencies and parastatals, Civil Society Organizations, and the like as observed by the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNCEA) it posits, “ ...more importantly writing about specific issues MDGs target get help to keep stakeholders accountable for their commitment and can help give journalist critical experience in writing good economic and development stories”. (p.40).

Table 4.13: Distribution of Journalistic Patterns used in the Coverage of SDGs I-IV by Daily Trust Newspaper

Categories		Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Total	Percentage
Editorials	Poverty	0	0	2	2	4	7.69%
	Hunger	1	4	3	1	9	17.31%
	Health	5	2	3	1	11	21.15%
	Education	6	8	7	7	28	53.85%
Total		12	14	15	11	52	1.67%
Features/Opinions	Poverty	0	1	3	2	6	3.55%
	Hunger	8	20	9	4	41	24.26%
	Health	23	49	3	5	80	47.34%
	Education	15	17	5	5	42	24.85%
Total		46	87	20	16	169	5.41%
News Analysis	Poverty	0	0	0	0	0	0.00%
	Hunger	11	16	19	6	52	44.83%
	Health	9	11	9	6	35	30.17%
	Education	1	9	11	8	29	25.00%
Total		21	36	39	20	116	3.72%
News stories	Poverty	82	74	111	122	389	13.97%
	Hunger	123	165	147	145	580	20.83%
	Health	266	183	192	230	871	31.21%
	Education	244	205	233	264	946	33.98%
Total		715	627	683	761	2786	89.20%
GRAND TOTAL		794	764	754	809	3123	100.00%

The above table shows that the coverage of SDGs I-IV was significantly recorded in form of news stories with 2786 issues representing 89.20 per cent widely followed by features/opinions with 169 record represented by 5.41 per cent, closely followed by news analysis that has recorded 116 issues representing 3.72 per cent the least among the story types was editorials which receive 52 issues representing 1.67 per cent. This indicates that *Daily Trust* relied heavily on the coverage of news stories related to SDGs I-IV and has not given reasonable attention by way of interpretative reporting, features and opinions both within and outside the newspaper's organization, the paper position on the coverage of SDGs I-IV through editorials page was also not given the much-needed attention.

Table 4.14: Distribution of Journalistic Patterns used in the Coverage of SDGs I-IV by The Guardian Newspaper

Categories		Jan-Mar	Apr-Jun	Jul-Sep	Oct-Dec	Total	Percentage
Editorials	Poverty	2	3	3	0	8	24.24%
	Hunger	0	0	4	2	6	18.18%
	Health	1	2	2	1	6	18.18%
	Education	2	1	5	5	13	39.39%
Total		5	6	14	8	33	1.14%
Features/Opinions	Poverty	12	5	1	2	20	9.05%
	Hunger	4	6	7	6	23	10.41%
	Health	15	16	20	11	62	28.05%
	Education	25	22	33	36	116	52.49%
Total		56	49	61	55	221	7.65%
News Analysis	Poverty	2	1	0	1	4	4.94%
	Hunger	2	0	0	2	4	4.94%
	Health	20	10	14	23	67	82.72%
	Education	2	0	2	2	6	7.41%
Total		26	11	16	28	81	2.80%
News Stories	Poverty	69	48	63	65	245	9.59%
	Hunger	32	53	81	42	208	8.14%
	Health	276	250	350	305	1181	46.22%
	Education	185	208	304	224	921	36.05%
Total		562	559	798	636	2555	88.41%
GRAND TOTAL		649	625	889	727	2890	100.00%

Table 4.14 above reveals that out of the 2890 total coverage from all the analysed four units, news stories records highest with 2555 issues representing 88.41 per cent across the SDGs I-IV, distantly followed by features/opinions with 221 issues corresponding to 7.65 per cent, the least across the four news stories are editorials and news analysis with 33 and 81 issues corresponding to 1.14 per cent and 2.80 per cent accordingly. The above findings encapsulate that, the *Guardian* newspaper reported SDGs I-IV mainly through news stories as the findings shown how it consumed the largest percentage of the total news stories coverage.

Table 4.15: Distribution of Journalistic Pattern used in the Coverage of SDGs I-IV by Daily Trust and The Guardian Newspapers

Categories		Daily Trust frequency	Percentage (%)	Guardian Frequency	Total frequency (%)	Total Frequency	Total percentage (%)
Editorials	Poverty	4	7.69%	8	24.24%	12	14.12%
	Hunger	9	17.31%	6	18.18%	15	17.65%
	Health	11	21.15%	6	18.18%	17	20.00%
	Education	28	53.85%	13	39.39%	41	48.24%
Total		52	1.67%	33	1.14%	85	1.41%
Features/Opinions	Poverty	6	3.55%	20	9.05%	26	6.67%
	Hunger	41	24.26%	23	10.41%	64	16.41%
	Health	80	47.34%	62	28.05%	142	36.41%
	Education	42	24.85%	116	52.49%	158	40.51%
Total		169	5.41%	221	7.65%	390	6.49%
News Analysis	Poverty	0	0.00%	4	4.94%	4	2.03%
	Hunger	52	44.83%	4	4.94%	56	28.43%
	Health	35	30.17%	67	82.72%	102	51.78%
	Education	29	25.00%	6	7.41%	35	17.77%
Total		116	3.72%	81	2.80%	197	3.28%
News Stories	Poverty	389	13.97%	245	9.59%	634	11.87%
	Hunger	580	20.83%	208	8.14%	788	14.75%
	Health	871	31.21%	1181	46.22%	2052	38.42%
	Education	946	33.98%	921	36.05%	1867	34.96%
Total		2786	89.20%	2555	88.41%	5341	88.82%
GRAND TOTAL		3123	100.00%	2890	100.00%	6013	100.00%

4.6: Journalistic Genres Used in the Coverage of SDGs I-IV by Daily Trust and The Guardian Newspapers: Discussion of Findings

Analysis from table 4.15 revealed that news stories have major proportion among the four-story types in the reportage of SDGs I-IV by recording the highest coverage of 88.82 per cent of 5341 issues far distantly followed by features/opinions with the largest disparity in the percentage of 6.49 per cent of 390 records, the least from the table is editorial with 85 issues representing 1.41 per cent, news analysis record a close proportion of 3.28 per cent of 197 issues. The highest record from news stories is not surprising as it is the dominant feature of

newspapers coverage as indicated in previous studies conducted on development communication (Yusha'u, 2014, Popoola, 2014, Onyeizu & Binta, 2014, and Odozi & Nyam, 2014).

The predominance of news stories in reporting development, news implied that press in Nigerian does not give an elaborative analysis in form of interpretative reporting, features/opinions and editorial pages in newspaper pages based on the study findings (table 4.15). While the press has a unique power to bring information once hidden or ignored into the public domain by highlighting the stories of the incalculable many who still suffer from the aching realities of poverty, hunger, health, education and the like. Journalists have the greatest tendency to sensitize public opinions and remind those in power how lofty work is left for them to be done. (Griffen, 2013).

Although news stories are important segment in newspaper pages, editorials stand for paper a position which invariably indicates how significant media are towards the actualization of SDG goals, nevertheless, while it is clear and undoubtedly that fulfilling the role of development watchdog is not easy, development news do not always persuade towards newspapers patronage. Journalists must be prepared to fight for development-related matters like SDGs coverage in the editorial room. They must also travel to the poorest regions and speak to the victims of incomplete promises. (Griffen, 2013, p. 11). In relation to this assumption, a former Prime Minister to New Zealand and former administrator of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Helen Clark once noted " In a media environment of increasing competition and shortened attention spans, pieces on MDGs don't always sell the most papers or attract the biggest audiences" (Griffen, 2013, p.12). This perspective was buttressed by Campbell cited in Kadiri and Raji (2015). Development news which was

described as hard and boring does not have the capacity to sell newspapers. People prepared non-development news with an element of entertainment, as he notified

Generally speaking, audience around the world seems disinclined to be interested in serious news media, tending to prefer news with at least an element of entertainment in it. Where choices are offered between entertainment-oriented and 'serious' news, audiences often seem to prefer the entertainment-based output.

This brings the need for the proper usage and application of media framing theory by the media in an attempt to fully actualize the concept of development communication into practice. It is well-known fact that poverty is rampant in Nigeria in 2018; a news report released by global development institutions (OXFAM and World Bank data) described Nigeria as having the largest extreme population recently overtaking India. Kazeem (2018). Meanwhile, hunger is increasingly going beyond imagination with the highest number of malnourished children and equally, among the adults, a joint report from the United Nations (UN) and European Union (EU) realized on April 12, 2019, described Nigerian among the world's hungriest people in the world Tomarade (2019). More so, Global Report on Food Crises (GRFC), 2019 stated that the number of people unable to meet their daily food needs without humanitarian assistance has been rising for several years. Health and well being are lagging behind and equally absence or poor quality education. A global report compiled by Development Finance International (DFI) and Oxfam, placed Nigeria bottom in a ranking of 157 nations. The report says Nigeria's social spending (mainly on health, education and social protection) is "shamefully low." And those meagre levels are reflected in reality as Nigeria is home to the highest number of out-of-school children (Kazeem, 2018).

Media has the capacity of focusing on these important societal challenges through frequent publicizing in newspaper pages hence, having a powerful role in drawing the attention of the governing bodies to the resolution of such societal problems. As the media framing theory

emphasized and elaborated by McQuail (2015), well presentable formats in form of editorials, features or in-depth interpretative reports with proper selection of words, making some important contextual references, backing the facts with statistical data from relevant sources, referencing with images and pictures related to stories to give it meaning will tremendously help to interpret the coverage on SDGs related matters. Meanwhile, it is fundamental to provide SDGs frame issues to a meaningful format consequently, that will influence the audience in the perception of story coverage set on recognizable and global development matters/issues such as Sustainable Development Goals.

4.7 Summary of Major Findings

- 1) The study found that health as an aspect of SDG (III) has the highest frequency of coverage with 2052 (38.42%) while poverty as SDG (I) has the least in coverage with 634 (11.87%). [table 4.3]
- 2) The study found that stories on SDGs I-IV has the highest coverage featured inside the two newspapers' pages with 2737(98.21%) and 2499(97.81%). While the lead stories and other front pages covered for 49(0.92%) and 45(0.84%) by the *Daily Trust* and the *Guardian* respectively.(Table 4.6)
- 3) The study also found 4237(70.46%) of the stories on SDGs I-IV in the *Daily Trust* and the *Guardian* are recorded positive. (poverty has 607 (89.80%), hunger, 652 (70.49%), while Health and education have 1401(60.54 %) and 1577(75.22%) respectively. (Table 4.9)
- 4) The study also discovered that the major actors or key players in the coverage of SDGs I-IV by the *Daily Trust* and the *Guardian* newspapers are Civil Society Organizations, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs), and Community Based Organizations with the highest proportion of 2293(42,93%) of the total 5341 coverage. (Table 4.12)

- 5) The study also discovered that 2555 (88.41%) of the stories on SDGs I-IV are covered in news stories, 390(6.49%) are in features, 197(3.28%) are covered in news analysis while 85(1.41%) are covered in editorials foam. (Table 4.1)

CHAPTER FIVE: SUMMARY, CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This chapter gives a synopsis to the whole content of the study, it started with a brief review of the background information of the study, objectives and significance that led to the conduct of the research; conceptual framework, as well as the relevant literature, reviewed related to the study, theoretical framework, methodological approach and techniques adopted by the study; presentation of data gathered and analysis of the collected data; at last, a conclusion and recommendations of the study was provided.

5.1 Summary

Having introduced the study in chapter one with the historical background, the chapter gives a review also in details statement of the research problems and what instigates to study in the field of development communication concentrated on a cohesive global development agenda. Considering the growing increase in the proportion of people living in poverty, hunger and devastating situation of health and education sectors, as well as the general poor well, being of the Nigerian citizens, the press has a pivotal role to help in eradicating of these societal challenges. Chapter one of this study raised five research questions in investigating the indispensable role of the Nigerian press in the course of development journalism.

Chapter two of this study provides an insight into the vital concept of development communication. The concept of development, and the role media has been playing to

development process, and contribution made has made to national development was also elaborated. It also dealt with underpinning theories that include agenda setting and media framing as the theoretical framework within which the study relied, the chapter more so, review some important literature relevant to the study conducted on different aspects of sustainable development in the field of development communication.

Chapter three of this study explored the methodological approach suitable to the conduct of the study and it explained why content analysis is appropriate to adopt in the course of data collection, techniques for the selection of sample and sampling procedure, census- the total coverage as a sampling technique, sample in the selection of newspapers, the universe of the study was all elaborated in this chapter. Meanwhile, coding sheet as an instrument for data collection, editions of the newspapers analysed, the descriptive method of data presentation, statistical analysis of data interpretation using scores and percentage in a tabular form was fully elaborated in chapter three of this study.

Chapter four of this research outlined the application of the methodological approach, instruments and procedures and structures mentioned in chapter three through the use of tables, percentages and scores that aid the presentation and interpretation of the data collected, the chapter was divided into two segments or components with the detailed analysis of the two newspapers studied under one segment. Overall, a combined table for both the *Daily Trust* and *Guardian* newspapers was applied in the course of answering the five research questions raised earlier in chapter one.

The chapter concludes by providing some general findings of the study that include: inadequate coverage of SDGs I-IV by the two newspapers under study more importantly when compared to Other SDGs or the issues that has little impact to the live of the majority populace; Issues related to poverty, hunger, health and education were not given the much-

needed attention on the newspapers pages under study. Generally speaking, it can be concluded that Nigerian newspapers are not given the maximum attention through agenda setting spectrum and media framing assumptions which invariably lead to promoting the virtues of Sustainable Development Goals I-IV, creation of public awareness and sensitization, committing the governing bodies are all part of the basic functions of the press to the overall actualization of SDGs programme; Nigerian media are to some extent applicable to the tenets of development communication tenets through positive coverage of SDGs I-IV it was the study findings that the SDGs I-IV coverage across the four units analysed was encouraging and supportive to government efforts of the said policy implementation and execution. The study findings also revealed that actors like Civil Society Groups, Non-government organizations, reports from medical experts and the like have played a significant role in the coverage of SDGs I-IV closely followed by Government agencies and parastatals.

The journalistic genres used in the coverage of SDGs I-IV was almost to ninety percent recorded as news stories as the findings reveal even though, news stories take a larger proportion in Nigerian newspaper pages, however, media propagation in form of interpretative and investigative reporting of issues related to poverty, hunger, health and education will help immensely towards execution of SDGs in the most appropriate manner, features or opinion were recorded very low in the course of the study investigation while editorials which stand as newspaper stance on issues of public interest and equally of national importance, the least attention was given by all the two newspapers considering the percentage recorded in the course of the study analysis.

5.2 Conclusion

Having summarized this study and its key findings, it can be concluded that media particularly newspapers in all societies remain a viable and veritable mean of informing

people and creating awareness on development related issues. The newspaper has a direct connection in promoting development agenda like SDGs. At one point in time policymakers, government civil societies, development organizations and private sectors acknowledged the important role the mass media can play in achieving development goals or targets. In relation to this, the researcher would like to re-emphasize on a statement made by a senior executive of the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), Narinder Aggarwala (1979) stresses that journalists covering the development beats is expected to: “critically examine, evaluate and report on the relevance of development projects to national and local needs, the difference between a planned scheme and its actual implementation and the difference between its impact on the people as claimed by the government and as it actually is” (cited in Dara, 2000, p. 164). This assertion made by Aggarwala accentuates the watchdog role of the press in development projects, programmes and even policies. The media represents the public in furnishing constructive criticism of government activities and it is various agencies, informing readers on how the development process is affecting them and highlighting grey areas that need to be adjusted that would contribute meaningfully to the lives of the people that are exposed to relevant information on development agenda.

Moreover, the important role of media in propagating development needs described by Edmund Burke in the late eighteenth century as the Fourth Estate of the Realm or, the fourth branch of government apart from the executive, legislature and judiciary (McQuail, 2006). This declaration supported the popular statement made by the 3rd American president (1801-1809) Thomas Jefferson, which categorically states that “were it left to me to decide whether we should have a government without newspaper or newspaper without government. I should not hesitate a moment to prefer the latter” cited in (Kadiri et al 2015). The supposition made by Jefferson made it clear the significant role media suppose to be charged in fostering

sustainable development in any society. This, however, made it mandatory for media to fully take charge of their watchdog role and ensure Sustainable Development Goals has achieved a remarkable result before its deadline of 2030 and also, there is a greater need to make a tremendous difference from what was obtained from the former MDGs in the volume of coverage, format and styles of reporting, consistent and prominent story placement in strategic areas, giving an elaborative analysis of reports in form of features, and in the editorial pages which are said to be an authoritative voice of media organizations thus, lead to the emancipation of development-related stories like that of SDGs thus, the principles of development journalism in an appropriate mode is expected to be highly maintained.

5.3 The Study's Contribution to Knowledge

Being one of the studies in development communication on the concept of sustainable development it is anticipated that the study would add to the available literature in the field of sustainable development, on one hand, Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in particular and the overall national development at large. The findings of the study are expected to catalyze change on the part of the press to shift from neglecting development related issues to constant consideration to sustainable development goals more importantly, with the prevalence rate of poverty and hunger, poor health condition and non-qualitative education confronted by Nigerian citizens, the press tends to change the trend using the outcomes of the study. It is hoped that the research would serve as a reference point by the all the relevant stakeholders to the successful implementation of SDGs in Nigeria.

5.4 Recommendations for Further Studies

Based on the conclusions drawn above, the following suggestions are recommended to advance the concept of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).

1. This study is purely quantitative, it is recommended that a further study should be conducted using both the quantitative and qualitative approaches of content analysis this would go deeper in understanding the context of development-related matters in a more analytical approach.
2. While the study focuses on the frequency of coverage and story positioning on SDGs, it is recommended that further studies should be carried out using space allocation parameter. In other words, counting on the frequency of occurrence and placement of stories are not the only determining factors, space allocated to such news categories are also significant to scrutinize. It is however suggested that allocation of space apportioned to development-related categories is far amount important for examination.
3. It is further recommended that studies should be carried out using other channels of communications. Newspaper is one of the important modes of communicating; there is a need to conduct further studies using other traditional and online modes of communications (Radio, Television and other online platforms) to examine the level of contribution made by such media in the development process.
4. The study limits its investigation for one year, it is highly recommended that further studies should be carried out in the subsequent years (2016 upward) on the ongoing implementation process of Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs).
5. It is important to to sensitize media professionals about the need to improve the quantity and quality of SDGs coverage in Nigeria which should include articles and analysis reflecting everyday struggles of local regions especially the condition of those living in the resource- poor settings. Doing so will help encouraging societies and decision- makers to prioritize the SDGs agenda in the decision-making process.

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APPENDIX I

CODING SHEETS FOR DATA COLLECTION

Code Sheet 1

Categories		Date	Date	Date	Date	Date	Total
Editorials	Poverty						
	Hunger						
	Health						
	Education						
Total							
Features/Opinions	Poverty						
	Hunger						
	Health						
	Education						
Total							
News Analysis	Poverty						
	Hunger						
	Health						
	Education						
Total							
News stories	Poverty						
	Hunger						
	Health						
	Education						
Total							
GRAND TOTAL							

Code Sheet 2

CATEGORIES		DATE	DATE	DATE	DATE	DATE	TOTAL
POVERTY	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)						
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)						
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)						
	Private Donors						
	Other Related SDGs on Poverty						
Total							
HUNGER	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)						
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)						
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)						
	Private Donors						
Total							
HEALTH	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)						
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)						
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)						
	Private Donors						
	Other Related SDGs on Health						
	Total						
EDUCATION	Government, Ministerial Bodies and Agencies (GMBA)						
	Civil Society Organizations (CSOs), Non-Government Organizations (NGOs) and Community Based Organizations (CBOs)						
	International Develop Partners(IPDs)						
	Private Donors						

	Other Related SDGs on Education						
Total							
GRAND TOTAL							

Code Sheet 3

CATEGORIES		DATE	DATE	DATE	DATE	DATE	TOTAL
POVERTY	Lead Story						
	Front Page						
	Inside Page						
	Centre Spread						
	Back Page						
Total							
HUNGER	Lead Story						
	Front Page						
	Inside Page						
	Centre Spread						
	Back Page						
Total							
HEALTH	Lead Story						
	Front Page						
	Inside Page						
	Centre Spread						
	Back Page						
Total							
EDUCATION	Lead Story						
	Front Page						
	Inside Page						
	Centre Spread						
	Back Page						
Total							
GRAND TOTAL							

Code Sheet 4

CATEGORIES		DATE	DATE	DATE	DATE	DATE	TOTAL
POVERTY	Positive						
	Negative						
	Neutral						
Total							
HUNGER	Positive						
	Negative						
	Neutral						
Total							
HEALTH	Positive						
	Negative						
	Neutral						
Total							
EDUCATION	Positive						
	Negative						
	Neutral						
Total							
GRAND TOTAL							

Code Sheet 5

Unit of analysis	Categories	Story Direction of coverage	Date	Date	Date	Date	Date	Total
Editorials	Poverty	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Hunger	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Health	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Education	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
Grand Total editorial								
Features/ Opinions	Poverty	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Hunger	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Health	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Education	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
		Grand Total features/opinions						

Code Sheet 6

Unit of analysis	Categories	Story positioning	Date	Date	Date	Date	Date	Total
News Analysis	Poverty	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Hunger	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Health	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Education	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
		Grand Total News analysis						
News Stories	Poverty	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Hunger	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Health	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
	Education	Positive						
		Negative						
		Neutral						
		Total						
		Grand Total news stories						

Code Sheet 7

Categories	Date	Date	Date	Date	Date	Total
Total						
Business/ Finance						
Housing/Transportation						
Environment/ Climate						
Infrastructure						
Industrialization						
Oil, Gas and Mineral Resource						
Scientific and technological						
Power and Energy						
Disasters						
Security						
Foreign/ International						
Law and Judiciary						
Humanitarian						
Women and Children						
Telecommunication/ Media						
National Assembly/Legislature Politics						
Labour						
Corruption						
Youth						
Governance/Government						
Crimes and Conflicts						
Total						

Code Sheet 8

Content Categories	Lead Story	Front page	Inside page	Back page	Total
Business/Finance					
Housing/Transport					
Environment/Climate					
Infrastructure					
Industrialization					
Oil, Gas and Mineral Resources					
Scientific/Technology					
Power and Energy					
Crime and Conflicts					
Disasters/Safety					
Security					
Foreign/International					
Law & Judiciary					
Humanitarian					
Women and Children					
Telecommunications/Media					
National Assembly/Legislature					
Politics					
Labour					
Corruption					
Youth					
Government/Governance					

APPENDIX II

2016 Calendar

Months of the year	Total No. of working days	Total No. of weekend days	Total
January	21	10	31
February	21	8	29
March	23	8	31
April	21	9	30
May	22	9	31
June	22	8	30
July	21	10	31
August	23	8	31
September	22	8	30
October	21	10	31
November	22	8	30
December	22	9	31
Total	261	105	366

Cite this article:

Author(s), Khadijah BAFFA HAMZA, (2023). "Coverage of Sustainable Development Goals (I- Iv) By The Daily Trust and The Guardian Newspapers". Name of the Journal: International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 18-113 , DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7770878> , Issue: 2, Vol.: 5, Article: 3, Month: February, Year: 2023. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

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